

D2.1

The R-Map model (v1)

University of Twente

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Abbreviations

Table 1: Abbreviations

RWA	Remote Working Arrangements
LAU	Local Area Unit
NUTS	Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics)
COVID	Coronavirus Disease
HEU	Horizon Europe
PSM	Participatory systems mapping
CLD	Causal Loop diagram
FCM	Fuzzy Cognitive mapping
WP	Work package
Del	Deliverable

Executive Summary

Remote working, initially referred to as telework or smart work, has been a subject of research since the 1970s. The emergence of advanced information technology has facilitated professional work beyond traditional office spaces, impacting urban and rural dynamics, transportation, environmental factors, economic structures, and social relations. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of remote working arrangements, highlighting gaps in policies, regulations, and the need for systematic impact assessment.

The HORIZON-EUROPE-funded R-Map Project (Mapping, Understanding, Assessing, and Predicting the Effects of Remote Working Arrangements in Urban and Rural Areas) seeks to comprehensively analyse the spatial, economic, and social effects of remote working arrangements, across Europe. Conducted by an international consortium from Greece, Turkey, the UK, the Netherlands, Italy, Austria, and Belgium, the project aims to understand and forecast the consequences of RWAs while providing actionable recommendations for policymakers.

Understanding the interconnected social, spatial, and economic impacts of RWA presents a significant challenge due to the complexity of its cause-effect relationships. To address this, Task 2.1 focuses on co-designing an integrated impact assessment framework—the R-Map model—which systematically maps these relationships. The R-Map model serves as a conceptual framework to assess the effects of RWAs on the spatial, economic, and social aspects of the urban-rural divide in EU regions. A co-design process to conceptualise the R-Map model engaged consortium partners, the R-Map Advisory Board, and domain and regional experts, ensuring an interdisciplinary approach. Key sub-objectives were:

- Knowledge Synthesis: Establishing a shared understanding of the urban-rural divide based on WP1 findings.
- Dimension Definition: Defining the spatial, economic, and social dimensions of the urban-rural divide in the context of R-Map.
- Key Factor Selection: Identifying critical factors influenced by RWAs across diverse regions.
- Factor Assessment: Semi-quantifying these factors with expert input to evaluate their significance.

The co-design process incorporated a review of participatory and analytical methods, including Causal Loop Diagrams, Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping, Participatory System Mapping, and Bayesian Belief Networks. A review of public and unconventional datasets (e.g., social media data) and WP1.5 survey results was also conducted.

R-Map Model Development and Key Findings

The model was co-designed using Participatory System Mapping, incorporating expert and experiential knowledge. The conceptual R-Map model features:

- Causal impact chains across spatial, economic, and social domains.
- A comprehensive causal network illustrating factor interdependencies.

The R-Map model distinguishes drivers of remote working (e.g., digital infrastructure, transport accessibility, taxation policies) from impacts across spatial, social, economic, and environmental domains. Key social impacts include health and well-being, caring responsibilities, and social cohesion. Spatial impacts include polycentricity, land consumption, multilocality, mobility patterns, and relocation. Economic impacts include

employee productivity, access to labour markets, and regional economic development. Additionally, socio-economic impacts—work-life balance, workplace loneliness, cost of living, and tourist/digital nomad living space demand—were identified. Carbon emissions was incorporated later as an environmental impact.

The model maps causal relationships between factors such as health and well-being, work-life balance, workplace loneliness, mobility patterns, polycentricity, and regional economic development. It distinguishes between direct and indirect causal relationships in specific causal chains, identifying mediators, confounders and colliders that influence impact assessments. The temporality of impacts varies, with short-term effects observed in workplace loneliness and work-life balance, while long-term effects emerge in spatial planning, land consumption, and regional economic shifts.

Consensus among partners confirmed the strong effects of RWAs on health and well-being, mobility patterns, multilocality, polycentricity, social cohesion, work-life balance, workplace loneliness, access to labour markets, and local/regional economic development. The study also highlighted the role of digital infrastructure and transport accessibility as key drivers of RWAs and polycentricity's broad influence across spatial and economic domains. The identification of mediators, confounders and colliders, along with the semi-quantification of indicators, will facilitate the transition of the conceptual R-Map model into a computational model. Bayesian approaches will be used to refine causal relationships and enhance predictive capabilities.

Future Research and Application

The conceptual R-Map model serves as a foundational framework for continued research to elaborate an integrated impact assessment model which will be extended into regional case studies under WP4. Future refinements will integrate additional datasets and statistical modelling to enhance predictive accuracy. Task 2.2 will focus on refining and validating the model using:

- Indicator formulation for factors identified in Task 2.1.
- Dataset harmonization for model implementation.

Bayesian statistical approaches to align surveyed knowledge with measured data, enabling predictive analyses. The R-Map project underscores the transformative role of remote working in reshaping urban-rural dynamics. By leveraging interdisciplinary expertise and empirical research, it provides a robust analytical foundation for policymakers and stakeholders to navigate the evolving landscape of work in an increasingly digitalized world.

1. Introduction

Remote working, in early studies often referred to as telework or smart work, can be defined as professional working that takes place outside the office/workspace with the use of IT technology. The occurrence and effects of remote working have been researched already since the 1970s (Adobati and Debernadi 2022). A strong focus of research conducted on remote working has ever since been on the multitude of potential positive or negative impacts of remote working on e.g. spatial arrangements in cities and regions, transport infrastructure and mobility on employees, environmental impacts such as air and noise pollution and carbon emissions, and economic and social impacts for both employers and employees, among other impacts.

The COVID-19 pandemic at the beginning of the 2020s gave a massive push not only to various remote working arrangements and technologies but also boosted research on both. Key findings (Krasilnikova and Keitel 2022) highlighted significant policy gaps and a lack of regulations and procedures to implement remote working arrangements (RWA). Further findings revealed that impacts of RWA can differ quite strongly between countries and regions, between economic sectors and can impact gender inequalities.

With the ongoing rapid development of information and communication technologies including the adoption of AI in many economic sectors, the way of working will further change profoundly in many branches, and it is likely to assume that flexible working arrangements are continuously increasing with remote working becoming a natural part of it. Considering that, it is essential to better understand the diverse impacts of remote working to devise suitable remote working policies harvesting its positive outcomes and impacts on societies and countries and mitigating the negative impacts.

1.1 Background and project context

This report is written in the context of the HORIZON-EUROPE (HEU) funded **R-Map Project (Mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of remote working arrangements in urban and rural areas)** (Project 101132497 — R-Map), which is conducted by an international consortium of academics and professionals from Greece, Turkey, UK, Netherlands, Italy, Austria and Belgium. The overall goal of the R-Map project is to understand, forecast and suggest ways to address the impacts of remote working arrangements on the spatial (including environmental), economic and social facets of the urban-rural divide in Europe. This goal first requires a comprehensive understanding of the diversity of RWA across Europe and the diversity of impacts and effects resulting from them which has been accomplished in WP1 (Deliverables 1.1-1.4).

Considering the insights of different RWA across Europe and the variety of impacts in the spatial, social and economic domains, an impact assessment model needs to be developed that allows to map, analyse and estimate future impacts of RWA and their relations under changing conditions. For this task, a basic impact assessment framework is required that is broad enough to cover the diversity of impacts and RWA across Europe and at the same time sufficiently flexible to be applied to varying contexts of diverse European regions. The development of the overall impact assessment framework and model is part of WP 2 while the application and contextualization of the R-Map model to various European regions is done in WP 4 of the R-Map project.

That said, in WP2 the development of the impact assessment framework and R-Map model relies strongly on the knowledge obtained in WP1, i.e. the insights about RWA across Europe and the elicitation of impacts of RWA on the spatial, social and socio-economic domain, as reported in scientific literature and observed in

practice. The goal of the project is to base the development of the R-Map model not solely on scientific insights reported in the literature as the evidence on RWA impacts is partly in its infancy and currently deriving novel insights resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic, but also include experiential and professional knowledge from regional and domain-specific experts through a co-design process.

1.2 Objectives and scope of work package 2 and task 2.1

The goals of WP2 entitled “Design of the R-Map model” are (i) to develop an Integrated Assessment Framework (the R-Map model) for assessing social, spatial and economic impacts of remote working arrangements at the European level, (ii) to develop a typology of EU regions based on how remote working arrangements have affected the spatial, economic and social facets of their urban-rural divide, and (iii) to define a taxonomy of economic and social impacts of remote working arrangements.

The objective of the here reported Task 2.1 is to co-design the R-Map model for assessing the effects of RWA on the spatial, economic and social facets of the urban-rural divide in EU regions. This objective entails the sub-objectives of (1) synthesizing the knowledge produced in WP1 to agree on a common understanding of the urban/ rural divide, (2) defining the spatial, economic and social dimensions of the urban-rural divide in the context of R-Map, (3) selecting the key spatial, social and economic factors of the urban/ rural divide that are affected by remote working arrangements in the different regions, and (4) assessing and semi-quantifying these factors in terms of their importance drawing on expert knowledge. Output of Task 2.1 is the conceptual design of the R-Map model including semi-quantified cause-effects impact chains across domains and an overview of suitable data sources and sets to inform the selected impacts.

Task 2.1 started with a review of participatory model-building methods and statistical methods for integrated impact assessment. Then, a review of publicly available datasets to inform spatial, social and economic factors representing impacts of remote working arrangements was conducted. This review also entails the inspection of unconventional data sources such as data derived from social media platforms, and an exploration of the data quality resulting from the large-scale survey conducted in WP 1.5. The co-design process as such consisted of 1 day co-design workshop at the University of Twente in September 2024, and 4 online (technical) workshops with consortium partners, advisory board members and domain and regional experts in which each iteration of the R-Map model was discussed and reflected upon. In between the workshop session, all partners were involved in the co-design via an online survey and review tasks.

1.3 Project partners and others contributing to the report

The co-design of the R-Map model was a collaborative effort led by the UT team. It actively involves all partners of the project consortium and the R-Map Advisory Board, as well as domain and regional experts to accommodate the inter- and transdisciplinary nature of the topic. All experts participated in the 1-day co-design workshop at the UT and the subsequent online validation workshop (see for details section 2.3 and annex table 1 for a detailed list of participants). Also, the so-called sister projects of the R-Map project, the WinWin4WorkLife (WW4WL) project (<https://winwin4worklife.eu>) and the REMAKING project (<https://remaking-project.eu>) were contacted and invited to contribute to the co-design process during the

online validation workshop. From these, WW4WL accepted the invitation and contributed valuable inputs to the process.

1.4 Outline of the report

In Section 2 methods for suitable participatory modelling and integrated impact assessment are discussed, terminological and methodological settings for the process are reported, and the methodology of the co-design process to develop the R-Map model for integrated assessment of social, spatial and economic impacts of remote working arrangements is documented. Section 3 entails a detailed description of the resulting R-Map model, particularly discussing and analysing all included factors and the relevant causal relations between them. Section 4 provides a thorough review of existing data sources to inform and quantify R-Map model factors. Section 5 provides a critical reflection of the resulting R-Map model, its strength and scientific value as well as its limitations and shortcomings in terms of application. The report closes in Section 6 with the conclusions and an outline of the next and follow-up steps in WP2 of the R-Map project.

2. Methodology

Section 2 reports on the methodology applied in Task 2.1. The objective of Task 2.1 is, in short, to conceptually develop the R-Map model as an integrated assessment model of remote working impacts. The basis for the model development is the literature review and expert consultation conducted in WP1 and the experiential knowledge of the entire R-Map consortium, the advisory board members and other invited experts. The methodological approach we choose is a participatory model-building approach using causal mapping methods embedded in a co-design process.

The section starts with a review of participatory causal mapping methods for integrated assessment (section 2.1). Section 2.2 summarizes the overall methodologic approach to the task and provides conceptual definitions and the key terminology. Section 2.3 reports the implemented co-design process.

2.1 A review of causal mapping methods for integrated impact assessment

In this section, we elaborate on the different causal mapping methods that can be utilized for integrated impact assessment. We discuss the most relevant methods with respect to the co-design of the R-Map integrated impact assessment model.

A causal diagram that represents cause-effect relationships within a system helps in understanding a certain phenomenon, e.g. impacts of remote working arrangements (Cunningham, 2021). Developing such a diagram requires integrating expertise derived from multiple sources, including theory, scientific models, expert input, personal observations and experiences, evidence from literature, intuition, and hypothesizing. As emphasized by Pearl & Mackenzie (2019), data alone cannot establish causality within a system; causal inference relies on constructing a causal diagram to examine the relationships of cause and effect within a system or phenomenon. Pearl (2009) specifically refers to directed acyclic graphs (DAGs), often used to structure Bayesian Networks and counterfactual analysis.

The co-design approach (Section 2.3) that is aimed at, in this task emphasizes the importance of participatory methods for constructing causal maps, involving experts and stakeholders to collectively identify system components and relationships. Participatory causal mapping encompasses a range of methods, from qualitative to quantitative, including Causal Loop Diagrams, Participatory System Mapping, Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping, and Bayesian Belief Networks. These methods are sometimes referred to as mind mapping, cognitive mapping, system mapping, or causal diagrams (Barbrook-Johnson & Penn, 2022).

As Barbrook-Johnson & Penn (2022) highlight, causal mapping techniques can be viewed as methods that help produce simplified models composed of a set of elements, the relationships between them, and the system boundaries being examined. Some approaches, like Causal Loop Diagrams, Participatory System Mapping, and Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping, prioritize a system-wide perspective. Others, such as Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs), focus more explicitly on designing and assessing interventions. Methods also vary in their level of quantitative analysis and ease of stakeholder participation. Figure 1 below illustrates how different system mapping techniques can be positioned based on their degree of quantification and the ease of participant

involvement. In practice, often a combination of system mapping methods is used to address a particular question.

Figure 1: The different system mapping methods, adapted from Barbrook-Johnson and Penn (2022)

In the following, we provide a brief overview of selected methods—Causal Loop Diagrams, Participatory System Mapping, Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping, and Bayesian Belief Networks—which are particularly relevant for the development of the R-Map model. These methods strike a balance between qualitative and quantitative approaches, enabling maximum co-creation while maintaining a high level of quantitative sophistication. By combining methods in a causal mapping exercise, we can secure broad inputs without compromising analytical rigor. These methods are presented in their increasing quantitative sophistication, moving from qualitative to quantitative approaches. For each method, we highlight its respective strengths and weaknesses, forming the basis for our selection criteria and linking the problem to the most suitable approach, as detailed in section 2.2. An overview of additional methods, such as Rich Pictures, Theory of Change, and other system mapping techniques, can be found in Barbrook-Johnson and Penn (2022).

Before delving into the methods, we introduce and define the common components of causal maps, as represented in Figure 2.

Network: A network consists of nodes (boxes) connected by edges (links). In causal system maps, these edges are typically directed, meaning they take the form of arrows pointing from one node to another

Nodes: These represent the key elements or variables in the system being analysed. These are the boxes within a network where edges meet.

Links (a.k.a. edges): These are the connections or relationships between nodes, visualized as lines or arrows that indicate causality or influence

Figure 2: Components of a causal map – the network formed of nodes and (directed) links

2.1.1 Causal Loop Diagrams

Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs), rooted in the System Dynamics approach to simulation modelling, are tools for visualizing and analysing the interdependencies and feedback dynamics within a complex system (Penn et al., 2013; Sterman, 2000). They are situated roughly in the middle of the qualitative-quantitative spectrum of causal mapping methods (Figure 1), leaning more towards the qualitative side. They provide insights into the dynamics of a system, with a particular focus on feedback loops as a central component and organizing structure for complex systems. Due to their emphasis on feedback loops and the strict use of variables for nodes, CLDs are a natural stepping-stone to simulation methods such as stock-and-flow diagrams and system dynamics (Barbrook-Johnson & Penn, 2022).

At the core of a CLD are nodes, which represent variables or system elements, arrows that depict causal relationships between them, and feedback loops (as depicted in Figure 3). The boxes, or nodes, can be anything that makes sense to consider as increasing or decreasing along a scale. Each arrow indicates the direction of influence, with a "+" signifying a positive relationship (where both variables increase or decrease together) and a "-" representing a negative relationship (where one variable increases while the other decreases, and vice versa). These relationships intertwine to form feedback loops, which can be classified as either reinforcing loops (R) that amplify changes through positive feedback or balancing loops (B) that stabilize the system through negative feedback. In a reinforcing loop, change in one direction is compounded by more change. For example, money in a savings account generates interest, which increases the balance in the savings account and earns more interest. Balancing loops, in contrast, counter change in one direction with change in the opposite direction. Balancing processes attempt to bring things to a desired state and keep them there, much as a thermostat regulates the temperature in a house.

Causal Loop Diagram

Figure 3: Components of a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD): nodes, links and feedback loops

An example relevant to R-Map is the relationship between the number of hours spent working remotely (used here as a working definition of Remote Work Arrangements, or RWAs) and polycentricity, as illustrated in Figure 4. A positive relationship can be mapped, where increased hours of remote work enhance the likelihood of individuals relocating or engaging in activities across multiple localities (multilocality). These immediate outcomes, in turn, may contribute positively to the emergence of new centres and the process of decentralization, collectively referred to as polycentricity. However, unlike causal loop diagrams (CLDs), which primarily emphasize feedback loops, this example does not include such a loop. The components integrated from various methods, including CLDs, will be discussed later in accordance with our specific requirements.

As Barbook-Johnson and Penn (2022) highlight, CLDs can be constructed in a participatory manner, where discussions during workshops serve as data. However, due to the rigour required to focus on a system's feedback loops in a participatory setting, decisions are often made by the modeler or researcher. On the downside, Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs) can be limiting due to their strong emphasis on feedback loops, which can concentrate a lot of power in the hands of the researcher, particularly during the creation of these loops. If feedback loops are not present or significant in the examined system, this method may be less effective. Additionally, being positioned in the middle of the qualitative-quantitative spectrum means that CLDs do not provide any quantitative analysis. As a result, without quantitative data, it can be challenging to meaningfully understand how multiple feedback loops will interact.

R-Map Example

Figure 4: Example of a causal chain in the R-Map model and positive relationships between factors

2.1.2 Participatory System Maps

Participatory System Maps (PSMs) are causal models of a system represented by a network of factors and their causal relationships (Barbrook-Johnson & Penn, 2022). These maps are typically annotated and layered with detailed information about the factors and their connections. Technically, PSMs are directed cyclic graphs, meaning that the connections between factors are represented by directed arrows and feedback loops can exist within the network. The maps are developed by stakeholders, usually through a series of workshops and meetings, with the participatory nature of their creation being of utmost importance. The analysis approach also relies heavily on stakeholder input, network analysis principles, and an examination of the ‘flow’ and chains of causal relationships—often referred to as ‘causal flow’, thereby creating submaps focused on exploring specific questions or purposes in a highly participatory and iterative manner, which are brought together to create larger maps at times. The nodes in the map are referred to as factors. They can come from any relevant domain; they do not need to be explicitly quantifiable or supported by data, but they should be expressed as variables, i.e. elements in the system that can increase or decrease. There are often special types of factors, such as outcomes or functions of the system that are of interest, or interventions that can be controlled. The connections in the map represent causal relationships, which can be positive (i.e., if A increases or decreases, B changes in the same direction), negative (i.e., if A increases or decreases, B changes in the opposite direction), or uncertain/complex (i.e., where causal relationships depend on other factors or contexts, or where the relationship is strongly nonlinear). PSM are in the middle of the spectrum between flexible and qualitative methods such as rich pictures and theory of change, and more formal quantitative methods, such as Bayesian belief networks and system dynamics. They are likely to work best when using systems mapping in a participatory and flexible manner, but with a structure given by clear definitions of how the model works and how it can be analysed. The main steps in the process involve deciding on the aim of the

project, defining the system boundary, stakeholder selection, process design, selecting focal and general factors, building the map, collecting factor and connection information, and validating the links. After the causal map is developed, these insights can be transitioned into a more quantitative model, which can then be further enhanced using data-driven indicators.

2.1.3 Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping

Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM), developed by Kosko (1992), is a semi-quantitative tool that integrates cognitive mapping and fuzzy logic to model and analyse complex systems. It is particularly effective for studying systems characterized by uncertainty, vagueness, or incomplete data, where interdependencies exist but are not empirically defined and bridges the gap between qualitative knowledge representation (Penn et al., 2013). FCMs are particularly useful in participatory settings, as they allow stakeholders to integrate diverse forms of knowledge, experiences, and perceptions into a single coherent model. FCM enables the construction of causal maps, where system components (nodes) and their relationships (edges) are represented. Participants collaboratively identify key system components, define relationships, and assign weights to capture both the causal structure and the relative importance of variables. These relationships are weighted on a scale from -1 to +1, indicating the strength and direction of influence.

FCMs are used to identify dominant drivers, feedback loops, and system behaviours under different scenarios. Nodes represent factors that can vary in magnitude (e.g., increase or decrease), while edges indicate causal links. Relationships may not require empirical data, making FCMs ideal for exploratory analyses. A distinguishing feature of FCMs is their focus on generating outputs that support scenario testing and projections or facilitating stakeholder discussions. This capability makes FCMs highly versatile for applications such as environmental management, policy analysis, urban planning, and risk assessment (e.g. Reckien et al. 2014).

As Barbook-Johnson and Penn (2022) highlight, there are two main approaches in FCM – causal and dynamic ones. The causal approach retains the original FCM framework, where link weights represent certainty in causal relationships. Factor values range from 0 to 1 (or sometimes -1 to 1), indicating the degree of activation or causation. For instance, a factor value of 1 suggests complete activation, while 0 indicates no activation. Edges reflect certainty about causation, with stronger magnitudes implying greater confidence. This approach answers questions like: “If we change one factor, how confident are we that other factors will change?” The dynamical approach focuses on how changes propagate through the system, producing dynamic representations of relative changes in factor values. Factor values, often any real number, reflect the magnitude of an effect, while edge weights (-1 to +1) represent the strength of influence. The model tracks system behaviour iteratively until factor values stabilize or form repeating cycles. This approach helps identify the most influential factors and how structural changes affect system dynamics. Both approaches use edge values to reflect the strength of causal relationships, but their interpretations differ. The causal approach emphasizes certainty in causation, while the dynamical approach examines the propagation of effects. In summary, FCM provides a flexible framework for exploring complex systems, accommodating uncertainty and facilitating participatory analysis. FCM has been used in a variety of different scenarios, including exploration of future scenarios of deforestation in the Amazon (Kok, 2009) and bio-based economy for the UK Humber region (Penn et al., 2013).

2.1.4 Bayesian Belief Networks

Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs) are suitable for developing probabilistic causal models (Barbrook-Johnson & Penn, 2022). Like other methods, BBNs consist of nodes (representing variables, factors, or outcomes in a system) and edges (depicting the causal relationships between these nodes). Each node has defined states (e.g., on or off, high or low, present or absent) with associated probabilities of being in each state. These probabilities are determined based on the states of the connected nodes, which have causal arrows pointing toward them. In probabilistic terms, nodes are 'conditionally dependent' on the states of the nodes with which they share a causal connection. A key distinction of BBNs is their acyclic nature—arrows flow in only one direction, and no cycles or feedback loops are present. This sets them apart from other methods, such as Causal Loop Diagrams and Participatory System Maps, which incorporate cycles and feedback mechanisms. BBNs are directional probabilistic graphical models that model conditional dependence through directed edges, and conditional independence through missing linkages (Pearl, 2014). Using Bayes' theorem, BBNs address problems in complex systems by representing joint probabilities for the factor states in a model. The term "belief" reflects the subjective specification of probability distributions and relationships, distinguishing Bayesian probability from the frequentist approach, which relies on observed event frequencies.

We can define three types of linkages and nodes based on network positions (Pearl & Mackenzie, 2019) which are useful for identifying control variables in multivariate regression analyses. This helps satisfying the "back-door criterion", i.e. blocking all non-causal paths two variables of interest, and prevents overestimation, underestimation, or spurious correlations (Cunningham, 2021). The linkage types are as follows:

Fork linkage: $a \leftarrow b \rightarrow c$

Collider linkage: $a \rightarrow b \leftarrow c$

Chain linkage: $a \rightarrow b \rightarrow c$

In a fork linkage, factor b acts as a "confounder," and controlling for it makes a and c independent. In a collider linkage, b is a "collider," representing a common effect, and controlling for it can create spurious correlations. In a chain linkage, b is a "mediator" that can potentially be excluded from the model to simplify it, as it does not independently cause changes.

For instance, in the R-Map framework, consider a causal chain like the one discussed in Section 2.1.1, linking RWAs to polycentricity, with two additional factors influencing relocation. Figure 5 illustrates this acyclic structure, where nodes are assigned binary states (e.g., high/low) and conditional probabilities. The table accompanying the diagram displays the probabilities of polycentricity states as influenced by its two parent nodes—relocation and multilocality.

This BBN can be employed in two ways:

1. Downstream analysis: Changing the states of specific factors to simulate hypothetical scenarios and observing their impact on downstream nodes. For example, with high relocation and multilocality levels, there is an 80% probability of observing high polycentricity and a 20% probability of low polycentricity.

- Upstream analysis: Investigating the probable states of contributing factors that lead to a specific outcome. For instance, analyzing the likelihood of different relocation and multilocality states that result in high polycentricity.

Figure 5: Example of a Bayesian Belief Network implementation in R-Map

While BBNs are highly versatile, they have certain limitations. Their acyclic nature prohibits feedback loops of any length, a constraint necessary for the mathematical calculations to remain valid. However, in complex systems where feedback loops are often key drivers of dynamics, this limitation can be partially addressed through "dynamic" BBNs, which represent the same variable at different time points using multiple nodes.

Despite this constraint, BBNs offer flexibility by incorporating broader system elements through conditional probabilities during map construction and analysis, even if these elements are not explicitly included in the network. This capability enhances their value, even when the network does not capture all potential factors. Additionally, a significant strength of BBNs is their ability to update probabilities as new data or evidence becomes available, making them particularly effective for adaptive analyses in dynamic and evolving systems.

2.2 Methodological approach and terminology

2.2.1 Methodological approach

The development of the R-Map model fulfils all 4 aspects that Penn et al. (2013) describe as the main characteristics of problems where causal mapping methods can help:

- (1) when stakeholder behaviour and decisions are pivotal to a system's development,
- (2) when detailed local knowledge is available but scientific data is lacking,
- (3) when addressing complex 'wicked' problems with no definitive solutions, and
- (4) when public or stakeholder participation is desirable or necessary.

The review of RWAs and their impacts conducted in WP1 of the R-Map project (D1.1 to 1.4) revealed that decisions and behaviour of stakeholders, e.g. policy makers, are crucial to how impacts play out in certain contexts. WP1 further showed that detailed knowledge of impacts is available across Europe and beyond, but scientific data and insights are limited to single case studies, often conducted in one region or country. The variety of impacts across these diverse case studies and contexts is a key indication of the wickedness of the problem next to its multi-disciplinary nature. This wickedness in turn requires the strong involvement of multiple stakeholders to address the challenges of impacts from RWA.

Based on the pros and cons of the different causal mapping methods elaborated above we conclude to use a Participatory Systems Mapping approach organized as a co-design process to develop the R-Map model. The PSM approach suits the iterative engagement of the R-Map consortium and other experts in the development of the R-Map model in a series of workshops. The given structure of workshops ensures a result within the limited time frame. The qualitative nature of PSM enables the contribution of stakeholders to the model despite the lack of data to quantify factors. Moreover, it retains critical details and serves as a foundation for transitioning to a more quantitative method—in this case, a Bayesian Belief Network. The Bayesian Belief Network allows us to address uncertainties in inferences and effectively manage missing variables through its probabilistic framework. A detailed description of the co-design research process is provided in section 2.3.

2.2.2 Terminology

For the participatory systems mapping approach embedded in a co-design process, we agreed on the following terminology.

The conceptual R-Map model is represented by a network of factors and their causal relationships. Factors included in the R-Map model need to fulfil the following characteristics (Table 2).

Table 2: Characteristics of Factors

Factors	Examples
<p>Specific and measurable</p>	<p>In contrast to themes such as 'technology,' factors are more precise and measurable, like 'broadband access' or 'technological literacy'</p>
<p>Elements that are either influenced by remote work or have the potential to impact other factors influenced by remote work</p>	<p>Since the objective of this exercise is to examine the impact of remote working arrangements, the focus is on factors like 'employee productivity' rather than drivers like 'internet quality'—unless they also represent outcomes</p>
<p>Elements that can increase or decrease in value due to other factors or over time</p>	<p>Demographic variables such as 'age' and 'gender' are constants and do not qualify as impact factors. They will most likely be included as control variables</p>
<p>Preferably neutral, without indicating a positive or negative shift</p>	<p>Instead of using distinctions like 'formation (or reduction) of new social ties' it is more appropriate to use neutral terms like 'social ties', 'social network' or 'support network'</p>
<p>Continuous or categorical with multiple categories</p>	<p>We avoid binary categories since they provide limited utility for modelling. For example, 'gender equity' is a more useful factor than simply 'gender.'</p>
<p>Ideally, state variables, not events or processes</p>	<p>Similar to stock variables, factors represent states that can increase or decrease over time; they are not 'events' (which are one-time occurrences) or processes (like 'gentrification'). A process like gentrification is better analysed through specific state variables such as 'real estate prices' or 'net migration of communities.'</p>
<p>Relevant to the focus of the study</p>	<p>In this exercise, factors are relevant if they are significantly influenced by remote working arrangements or are sensitive to them. While gentrification might be an interesting phenomenon to study, unless there is substantial evidence or rationale to include it, it may fall outside the scope of this analysis</p>

Factors can represent spatial as well as social or economic impacts of RWA. During a first screening of all potential factors as suggested in WP1, it became clear that some factors are rather suited to affect the implementation of RWA (such as digital infrastructure) while others are rather affected by the implementation of RWA (e.g. health impacts). To represent this distinction, we distinguish between drivers and impacts (see Figure 6).

Factors may occur as impacts that are affected by certain RWA (e.g. Health and Wellbeing) as well as drivers that affect the implementation of certain RWA (e.g. Digital Infrastructure Accessibility). For the sake of conceptual clarity, we separate in the conceptual R-Map model drivers from impacts as depicted in Figure 6.

Drivers and Impacts

Figure 6: Separation of drivers and impacts

While drivers affect RWA directly and are mutually independent, factors are represented in the R-Map model as a network with causal relationships between them. The network of impacts results in cause-effect relationships between various impacts that can include mediating factors (mediators), confounding factors (confounders) and collider factors (colliders). A mediator is a factor that does not independently cause any change to other factors, confounders are factors that influence both the dependent variable and independent factors, and colliders are factors that are common effects in a specific causal chain (see Figure 7). Section 3.3.5 provides examples of causal chains in the R-Map conceptual model.

Confounders, Colliders and Mediators

Figure 7: A factor acting as a a) confounder, b) collider and c) mediator depending on the network position in the map

The causal relations between the impacts are represented as links. These links can represent certain strengths of relation between two factors (weak, medium, strong relation), they can represent a positive (if factor A increases, factor B also increases) or a negative (if factor A increases, factor B decreases, and vice versa) relation, and they represent a relative temporality of the relation between two factors, i.e. these relations may occur either at short, medium or at the long term.

As discussed above, the impacts of RWA might differ in different contexts and constellations and vary if studied for certain sociodemographic groups or economic sectors. Impacts further differ concerning the specific RWA arrangements implemented. All these aspects are strictly speaking not part of the R-Map model but represent the so-called control variables that the R-Map model is to be checked for. A classification of typical control variables is provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Classification of Factors

Factors	Definition	Example
RWA	Metrics of professional working that takes place outside the office/workspace with the use of IT technology	The amount of time working remotely.
Branches/economic sectors	Single economic sectors having potentially specific RWAs	Industrial branches, services, education and training, etc.
Contextual factors	Spatial variations in impacts attributed to characteristics of the built and social environment	Urban or rural areas, countries, population density, etc.
Compositional factors	Differences in the composition of a group/region in terms of individual socioeconomic status or behaviour	Gender, age, income levels, household characteristics, etc.

2.3 The R-Map model co-design process

As outlined above, the goal of the co-design process is to (i) synthesize the knowledge produced in WP1 to arrive at a common understanding of the urban/ rural divide, (ii) define the spatial, economic and social dimensions of the urban-rural divide in the context of R-Map, (iii) select the key spatial, social and economic factors of the urban/ rural divide that are affected by remote working arrangements in the different regions and (iv) assess and semi-quantify these factors in terms of their importance drawing on expert knowledge and geographic context. In WP1 of the R-Map project, partners reported relevant impacts of remote working arrangements from broad literature reviews and expert interviews focusing on the social, spatial, and economic aspects of RWA that serve as input to the co-design process.

The co-design of the R-Map model is set forth through a series of workshops involving the consortium partners (UT, AUTH, UB, KU, SEERC, SURREY, RIM, Q-PLAN, WR, ARX), members of the advisory board of the projects, and other regional and domain-specific experts. The sequence of workshops includes one full-day physical workshop at the University of Twente with all consortium partners, the advisory board members and invited experts, three online workshops with the consortium partners, and a virtual validation workshop again with the advisory board, domain/ regional experts and potential users to present the results of the co-design process and seek feedback. In between the workshops, we sought additional input from partners via a survey and a request to revise and comment on factor definitions.

Figure 8: Schematic overview of the co-design process

2.3.1 The Co-design Workshop at UT

The starting point of the development of the R-Map model was the one full-day co-design workshop at the UT with all consortium partners, AB members and invited regional and domain experts (see the full list of participants in Annex 1). The co-design workshop was conducted on September 4, 2024, at the UT in Enschede, the Netherlands.

The purpose of the workshop was to identify relevant factors from the reports of WP 1 and the experiential knowledge of all participants, to get acquainted with and practice the participatory system mapping method, and to draft relations between selected factors as a basis for the R-Map model. WP1 task leaders were requested to identify and present the ten most important factors from their studies as input to the workshop. The workshop was structured into two main steps (see Figure 9). The first step focused on knowledge synthesis, which involved the integration of scientific and experiential knowledge and the discussion of relevant factors. The second step introduced participatory systems mapping in groups to start the conceptual design of the R-Map model.

The workshop structure is described in Figure 9. The host's presentation outlined the exercise's objective, explained the terminology and methodology (see section 2.2), and described the tasks. Following this, each task leader (Task 1.1 to Task 1.4) presented their identified factors, after which participants were assigned one or two factors each. These factors were written on colour-coded cards, with each colour representing the various dimensions covered by the task leaders. The assignment of factors to participants was based on participants' expertise. The participants were then paired with someone with the same-coloured card to discuss and reflect on their factors in line with the host's instructions. This pairing promoted domain-specific discussions. Then, participants were distributed into mixed groups of 7 to 8 people across four tables, with an

additional table for three online participants. The distribution ensured a balanced representation of participants from different backgrounds at each table. The task of this step was to discuss and refine, if necessary, the factors and add eventually missing factors in cross-disciplinary discussions. Once the factors were established across all tables, a joint plenary session was held to review the factors and eliminate redundancies. The participants then voted on the factors, ranking them based on their relevance to the project. Each participant had five votes to allocate. The top 15 factors, based on the voting results, were selected for the next stage of the exercise, where links were drawn between the factors. This process helped maintain manageability by limiting the number of links. In the final stage, participants, divided into the same breakout groups, used the selected 15 factors to draw causal directional links, redefining, omitting, or adding factors where necessary. The maps generated during the workshop are provided in the Annex (Annex 4, Figures 1 to 5). The criteria used to define factors are explained in section 2.2 (Table 2).

Figure 9: Workflow of the co-design workshop

2.3.2 First Technical Workshop

The purpose of the first technical workshop, conducted at the end of September 2024 online, was to consolidate and reflect on the results achieved in the co-design workshop at UT. Members of all consortium partners participated in the workshop. In preparation for the first technical workshop, the UT team rephrased a few original factors based on the results from the co-design workshop and started defining relevant factors that were identified through the voting at the co-design workshop.

First, the results from the participatory mapping exercise conducted in groups at the UT were presented and discussed. Part of the discussion was the rephrasing of single factors in line with the agreed characteristics of factors. Second, a consolidated network map of impacts that integrated the results from the 5 groups was

presented. This integrated map served to discuss once again the distinction between drivers and impacts as well as the role of confounding and mediating factors in the R-Map model. Further various options to visualize the R-Map model were discussed.

At the end of the workshop, partners were asked to comment on the definitions of factors before the next workshop.

2.3.3 Second technical workshop

The purpose of the second technical online workshop, conducted in October 2024, was to finalize the selection and definition of factors included in the R-Map model and to focus on the participatory mapping of causal relations between factors. Members of all consortium partners participated in the workshop.

The final list of factors to be included in the R-Map model was presented in the workshop and approved by all partners. This final list resulted from the previous discussions and the comments of partners on definitions and rationale of factors. The second part of the workshop focused on the causal relation between factors. The already mapped relations were reviewed, and a few new ones were added. Also, a new visualization of the R-Map model, that presents impacts according to their temporality (short vs. long-term impacts) and their degree of aggregation (aggregated vs. disaggregated impacts) was discussed. Disaggregated impacts cause effects that are experienced on an individual or household level while aggregated effects occur at a region level.

To obtain detailed insights on the relevance and nature of causal relations between factors, the UT team set up a survey that asks to indicate the strengths (weak, medium, strong), temporality (short, medium, long-term), and directionality (positive, negative) of each already mapped link. Each R-Map consortium partner was asked to answer one survey before the next workshop, resulting in a sample of 10 answers.

2.3.4 Third technical workshop

The purpose of the third technical online workshop was to discuss the results of the partner survey on the relevance and nature of causal relations between factors and to finalize the conceptual design of the R-Map model. Members of all consortium partners participated in the workshop.

10 partners had answered the survey on causal relations between factors. The following characteristics of the relations were analysed through the survey

- Degree of Consensus on Causal Relationship: Does Factor A cause a change in Factor B?
- Strength of Causal Relationship: What is the strength of the relationship between Factor A and B?
- Type of Causal Relationship: Does an increase in Factor A cause an increase in Factor B?
- Temporality of the Relationship: How long does the relationship take to realize?

Overall, the results of the survey confirmed many of the assumed relationships. Further, a large degree of agreement between partners regarding the cause-effect relations of impacts from RWA was found.

The final part of the third workshop focused on the revision of the R-Map model based on the results of the partner survey. Single relations were removed due to a low level of agreement on the relevance or direction of the relations or a large degree of uncertainty.

2.3.5 Validation workshop with experts and advisory board members

The purpose of the validation workshop was to present the ongoing conceptual development of the R-Map model to experts outside the R-Map consortium and to obtain feedback on the relevance and significance of the results obtained. Next to the consortium partners, the validation workshop was attended by some advisory board members and three representatives of the sister project WinWin4WorkLife (<https://winwin4worklife.eu>). As input to the discussion the entire co-design process and results obtained were presented. The focus of the presentation was on the identified factors, the results from the partner survey, and the draft conceptual R-Map model.

The overall outcome of this validation was a large degree of confirmation of the results and findings from the co-design process. The advisory board members confirmed that their expectations raised during the co-design workshop at the UT were overall met. The members of the sister project stated that they work on their project with a very similar set of factors they consider relevant. Upon their recommendation, one additional factor (relocation) was added to the set of factors which makes a specific cause-effect chain in the R-Map model much better understandable to others.

3. The conceptual R-Map model

The section elaborates on the result of the co-design of the R-Map model. In section 3.1 the knowledge and insights collected in WP1 are summarised. Section 3.2 provides a detailed discussion of the selected factors included in the R-Map model while section 3.3 elaborates the conceptual design of the R-Map model. Section 3.4 finally looks into the transition to Task 2.2 where the conceptual R-Map model is going to be implemented.

3.1 Knowledge Synthesis from WP1

WP1 of the R-Map project focused on "setting the scene" by examining the current state and prospects of remote working arrangements (Task 1.1), analysing the spatial effects of RWA across the EU and specific regional case studies (Task 1.2), assessing its impacts on working and living conditions (Task 1.3), and gaining a deeper understanding on potential socio-economic effects of RWA (Task 1.4). Key outcomes were summarized in reports (Deliverables 1.1 to 1.4), which are briefly summarized below. Following this, we highlight the key impact factors proposed by each partner as inputs for Task 2.1.

3.1.1 Deliverable 1.1: Current status and emerging trends of remote working arrangements in Europe and beyond

Deliverable 1.1 outlined that the nature of work is transforming as traditional offices give way to flexible environments like homes, co-working spaces, and informal settings. This shift, accelerated by COVID-19 and technological advancements, expands the global talent pool but also highlights disparities in access to remote work. These disparities stem from factors such as labour policies, infrastructure, digital skills, and socioeconomic development, with rural areas and less developed economies lagging compared to urban centres. The key findings are listed below.

- **Infrastructure and Skills Gaps:** Rural areas often lack digital infrastructure and skilled human capital, limiting their participation in remote work.
- **Policy Disparities:** While many EU countries have similar remote working policies, differences in governance, implementation, and protections of employees (e.g., health, safety, and privacy) persist. An effective monitoring of the governance and implementation of remote working arrangements is considered essential.
- **EU Digitalisation Goals:** Regional disparities in infrastructure and technology hinder the EU's vision of a unified digital market and digital sovereignty.
- **Stakeholder Consensus:** Remote work is here to stay, requiring clear legal frameworks and inclusive policies addressing rights, safety, and costs for remote workers.
- **Corporate and Cultural Impacts:** Remote work is reshaping corporate culture, managerial styles, and internal policies, underscoring the need for further research into its long-term effects.

3.1.2 Deliverable 1.2: Spatial implications of remote working arrangements across Europe and beyond

Deliverable 1.2 examined how the shift to remote work is reshaping urban and rural landscapes, influencing housing preferences, mobility patterns, energy use, and spatial dynamics. It focused on the driving factors behind new working spatialities, with an emphasis on place-based policies and insights from case studies and local actor interviews to contextualize regional impacts. The key findings mentioned are:

- **Emergence of New Working Spatialities:** Remote work has led to the rise of coworking spaces, digital hubs, and multilocality (operating across multiple locations). These trends are reshaping urban development, land use, real estate, mobility, social interactions and community dynamics.
- **Urban and Rural Transformations:** Urban centres, particularly central business districts, are declining, while suburban and peri-urban areas are experiencing growth, revitalizing smaller cities. Housing demand is shifting towards suburban and rural areas with more space and better living conditions, reflecting changing preferences.
- **Urban-Rural Dynamics:** Remote work can either bridge or widen the urban-rural divide, depending on how well opportunities are integrated into local economies and supported by policies.
- **Mobility:** Changes in commuting patterns (decrease of daily commute, longer commutes, altered peak hours etc) have been observed due to increased remote work.
- **Remote work's environmental impact is mixed:** reduced commuting emissions are potentially offset by higher home energy use, raising sustainability concerns.

3.1.3 Deliverable 1.3: Potential effects of remote working arrangements on the working and living conditions

Deliverable 1.3 findings revealed that remote work impacts workplace dynamics, living conditions, individual health and well-being. Organizational factors, such as engagement, satisfaction, and workplace culture, are explained to be closely tied to mental health which requires careful monitoring. The key findings are listed below:

- **Workplace Dynamics and Well-being:** Remote work can foster detachment from workplace culture, widening gaps between remote and on-site employees.
- **Living Conditions and Family Dynamics:** Altered relationships with environmental factors and service access affect living conditions. Caregiving responsibilities and gender norms heavily influence remote work experiences, with women often struggling more to balance work and caregiving.
- **Work-Life Balance and Health:** Remote work improves flexibility, reducing stress and fatigue, but extended working hours can offset the benefits of reduced commuting. Positive health behaviour (e.g., physical activity, diet, and sleep) is susceptible to blurred work-life boundaries, risking harmful habits. Organized remote work can improve mental health and behaviour but risks isolation and loneliness.

3.1.4 Deliverable 1.4: Understanding the potential socio-economic effects of remote working arrangements

Deliverable 1.4 details that many organizations are already advanced in implementing remote work, though differences exist between the public and private sectors and between large employers and SMEs. Remote work often shifts certain costs to employees, intentionally or unintentionally, and its benefits and drawbacks are unevenly distributed based on characteristics like gender, age, caregiving responsibilities, and home location. Emerging trends, such as digital nomadism remain underexplored, particularly regarding challenges like taxation and social security, which are amplified in cross-border contexts. The key findings are mentioned below under the categories of social, economic and socio-economic impacts:

1. **Social Impacts:** Gender and Age – Women gain flexibility but face higher stress and mental health challenges. Younger workers struggle with performance; older workers need telework training and gradual adaptation. Social isolation and unsuitable workspaces impact older workers' well-being.

Work-Life Balance – Flexible hours support family life but blur work-home boundaries, reducing focus and productivity. Balancing professional responsibilities with childcare can be stressful.

Social Network – Social isolation is a significant concern due to remote work impacting productivity, performance and well-being

2. **Economic Impacts:** Tax, Social Security, Pension, Salary parity and Insurance – Equitable pay models updated social security, and insurance policies for remote-specific risks (e.g., ergonomic injuries and cybersecurity) are essential.

Property Market – Remote work drives suburban and rural housing demand and land values, reducing urban office use and land values in city centres.

3. **Socio-economic Impacts:** Transport and Accessibility – Reduced commuting lowers costs, stress, emissions, alleviates congestion and boosts gender equity and inclusivity for individuals with disabilities

Regional Development: Decentralization supports smaller cities, boosts local economies, and enhances employment resilience.

3.1.5 Factors suggested by Del. 1.1 to 1.4 for UT co-design workshop E

Each WP1 partners responsible for a Deliverable (1.1 to 1.4) was asked to suggest plus/minus 10 most important factors, i.e. the most relevant impacts from remote working arrangements, as input to the co-design workshop. The identified factors are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Key factors identified by WP1 task leaders as input to the UT co-design workshop

Task/Deliverable	Suggested Factors
1.1	Remote work index; legal inadequacy; connectivity; internet speed; internet quality; affordability of internet; digital skills; cost of living; good life enablers; gender distribution; seniority
1.2	City size; suburbanisation; multilocality; urban decentralisation; land consumption; land-use change; gentrification; urban-rural divide; transport; local infrastructure stress; energy demand
1.3	Wellbeing and mental health; precarity level; autonomy; non-attachments degree; sustainable occupational health and safety services in RWA; flexibility types; household dynamics-related burden; work-life balance; presenteeism; workplace loneliness; level of inequalities; level of accessibility; RWAs literacy; awareness level; technological readiness; labour participation opportunities; work intensity
1.4	Gender; age; caring responsibilities; social network; property market; transport and accessibility; local tourism economy; insurance

During the co-design workshop at the UT, these factors were discussed and revised in mixed groups with experts and advisory board members (co-design process step 1). The goal of the discussion was to agree on the set of factors in a wider group and to revise them according to the defined characteristics of factors (see table 1 in section 2.2.2; see the revised list of factors that the group agreed on in Annex 2).

3.2 Relevant factors in the R-Map model (Drivers and Impacts)

As explained above, the R-map model distinguishes factors into drivers and impacts, with additional classifications as confounders or mediators based on their network position (see section 2.2). In the following, the final selected factors resulting from the co-design process are presented and discussed. The challenges of the co-design process were to capture the multitude and diversity of impacts resulting from remote working arrangements in the R-Map model, select the most relevant factors, and define the factors precisely to avoid any misconception. Another boundary condition of the co-design process was to agree on a limited set of factors (around 15 to 20 impacts) to be included in the R-Map model to achieve a workable model that allows quantifying impacts of RWA in Task 2.2.

The factors and their classifications are further detailed in the following subsections. A list of factor definitions, which was utilized as a collaborative document for discussions, is provided in Annex Tables 3 and 4.

3.2.1 Drivers

The co-design process identified four key drivers of remote working arrangements: digital infrastructure accessibility, access to local amenities, transport accessibility, and taxation/social insurance regulations.

1. **Digital Infrastructure Accessibility:** the driver was initially suggested under internet quality (e.g. speed, bandwidth) and internet affordability by Del. 1.1 and revised and consolidated in the discussions during the co-design workshop. The factor captures the access to high quality (in terms of speed and coverage) and affordable internet. Citing Eurofound (2022), Task 1.1 identifies technical infrastructure (e.g., broadband accessibility) as a relevant driving factor which might explain variations in the prevalence of telework noted across different countries, and between urban and rural areas.
2. **Access to Local Amenities:** The factor was added during table discussions in the co-design workshop by two groups who called it 'access to local amenities and opportunities' and 'city facilities (transport, health care, amenities)'. It was merged into one factor during the plenary session and recognized as a significant factor during the voting process. Streamlining with a suggestion of Task 1.2, as to what all elements comprise amenities, the factor was finally understood as access to green areas, shopping, recreation, education, sports and community facilities, co-working spaces, etc. The factor is also understood to cover the dimension of quality of life incorporating the factor 'good life enablers', suggested by Task 1.1.
3. **Transport Accessibility:** The impacts on transport and mobility from remote work were identified as significant by Tasks 1.2 and 1.4. However, during discussions in the co-design workshop, it was classified as a significant driver, which rather influences the relocation decision of employees and thus can be characterised as a driver of RWAs. It is understood as a measure of the ease of reaching (and interacting with) destinations or activities distributed in space. A place with "high accessibility" is one from which many destinations can be reached with relative ease. It also covers aspects of accessibility to work and travel time and costs.
4. **Taxation, Social Security, Insurance Regulations:** This factor was originally suggested by Task 1.4, and emphasized by other partners during the technical workshops. This factor serves as a broad container term that encompasses economic drivers of RWA including taxation, social security, pensions, and insurance which play out differently in different contexts. The factor captures different regulations and laws governing how individuals and businesses are taxed, including income, sales, and corporate taxes, which are typically set at the country or regional level. The factor encompasses tax rate differences between countries, double tax arrangements, social security and insurance framework. As mentioned above, D1.1 elaborates that while many EU countries have similar remote work policies, differences in governance, implementation, and worker protections (e.g., health, safety, and privacy) persist, requiring effective monitoring. Further as elaborated in D1.4, remote work necessitates the development of new remuneration models that are equitable and motivating. Furthermore, insurance policies, originally designed for physical workplaces need to be updated to cover remote work environments, ensuring workers' rights and protection regardless of the work location. Due to its role as a policy lever, this factor is understood to be a driver.

3.2.2 Impacts of RWA

As analysed in WP1, impacts of RWA occur across various domains. During the co-design process, the R-Map team agreed to distinguish spatial, social, economic and socio-economic domain impacts. The spatial domain also includes one environmental factor (carbon emissions) to avoid having a 5th domain. Along these four dimensions, the selected factors representing the impacts of RWA in the R-Map model are discussed in detail below. For an overview of factors that result from the co-design process (section 2.3) see Figure 10.

Impacts

Social Impacts

Spatial Impacts

Economic Impacts

Socio-economic Impacts

Figure 10: Impact factors included in the conceptual R-Map model

3.2.2.1 Spatial impacts

The spatial impacts of RWA include factors that describe changes in land use, transport patterns and spatial manifestation of socioeconomic factors. Five spatial impacts are identified: polycentricity, land consumption, multilocality, mobility patterns, and relocation, with carbon emissions later added as an environmental impact.

- 1. Polycentricity:** The factor was originally suggested by Task 1.2 as suburbanisation, urban decentralisation and new centralities and was subsequently clubbed into polycentricity, considering the preferences of state variables over processes in the interest of measurement. Polycentricity can be understood as a spatial phenomenon where at a regional scale multiple centres of similar size and importance exist, and at an urban scale, multiple neighbourhoods or sub-centres of similar importance exist. As described in D1.2, polycentricity could be a multi-scale phenomenon. At a regional scale, it implies the rise of small/medium-sized cities due to RWAs, while at a metropolitan scale, it implies decentralization towards the outskirts of the city. D1.2 recognises the emergence of new spatialities due to multilocality or relocation. These trends are reshaping urban development, land use, and the real estate market. Further, the report defines decentralization as the migration of (high-skilled) workers outside of the city centre to the immediate/inner suburbs within commuting distance, which can in turn lead to urban sprawl. The report cites Hölzel et al. (2023) and claims of a notable shift in the demand for office space during the COVID-19 pandemic. Similarly, Mariotti et al. (2021) and Biagetti et al. (2024) highlight the decrease in human presence in central neighbourhoods and increased demand for housing in less congested and more affordable areas outside urban cores.
- 2. Land Consumption:** Also originally suggested by Task 1.2, land consumption can be understood as the expansion of built-up area for human settlements. Task 1.2 defines land consumption in terms of the expansion of residential areas into previously undeveloped areas (due to more affordable housing options, less congestion and proximity to nature). They report that multilocality exacerbates land consumption by increasing the number of vacant or intermittently occupied homes.
- 3. Multilocality:** D1.2 defines multilocality as the maintaining of residences and activities in multiple geographic locations at the same time. It cites Greinke and Lange (2022), who in their study in three rural districts in Germany, report that multilocality prevents complete relocation from rural to urban areas due to strong ties to family and friends. The potential impacts discussed include housing prices being driven up, new construction, reduced affordability and vacancy in rural areas (Greinke and Lange, 2022; Weichhart and Rumpolt, 2015); increased land consumption, travel distance and car-based commute, benefits to local economy, but pose a challenge in developing strong social ties and engagement in local civic activities (Danielzyk et al., 2020).
- 4. Mobility Patterns:** Like the driving factor taxation, social security, insurance regulations, the factor mobility pattern also acts as a broad container term. Originally the factor was suggested by Task 1.2 as 'transport infrastructure' and by Task 1.4 as 'transport and accessibility'. Task 1.2 further elaborated that the factor stands for a shift in mobility and car usage patterns. More specifically, it stands for changes in the usage of public transport, and increased reliance on private vehicles. This is also suggested by Deliverable 1.4. The factor was rephrased initially during the co-design workshop as 'shifts in modes of transport' based on the Swedish experience which suggests the maximum shift was observed in the usage of different modes of transport than any other commuting behaviour. However, based on interviews conducted for Task 1.2, the Dutch experience suggests a shift in the purpose of commuting as well. Therefore, the factor was defined broadly as - patterns of human movement

facilitated by public or private transportation, encompassing two aspects: the choice of transport modes and the purpose of trips.

5. **Relocation:** The factor was added after the workshop with the sister project, AB members and regional experts. The sister project WinWin4WorkLife (WW4WL) acknowledged the synergies in the two projects and more specifically their focus on similar dimensions, with 'relocation' as an important component in their study. We also observed 'relocation' studied as an important mediating factor between remote work and housing and the real estate market. Additionally, it also allowed us to clarify the R-Map conceptual model, as will be elaborated further. Thereafter, upon further discussions with the partners, the factor was introduced and can be understood as the decision to move someone's place of living.
6. **Carbon Emissions:** The factor was added during the second technical workshop with the project partners. The impacts of RWA on carbon emissions were already studied several years ago. It is mainly affected by the travel behaviour of employees and their locational choices. Therefore, the above-outlined factors of mobility pattern, multilocality and polycentricity are mediating factors to carbon emissions. Various studies conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic revealed a decrease in carbon emissions due to a higher share of home working and reduced commuting activities by car (Roberto et al. 2022). In certain contexts, this energy saving might be eaten up by increased energy consumption during homework and other behavioural changes of remote workers (Marz and Sen 2022).

3.2.2.2 Social impacts

Social impacts represent the impacts of RWA on the life and living conditions of the employees. Three social impacts were identified including health and well-being, caring responsibilities, and social cohesion. These are described below.

1. **Health and Wellbeing:** Originally suggested by Task 1.3, the factor is defined as capturing impacts on physical health, mental health, social and family, work-related needs, and health behaviours - physical activity, diet, and sleep (according to EU-OSHA, 2023). Also, as mentioned in D1.3, the WHO emphasizes a holistic approach to well-being, encompassing physical and mental health as well as social dimensions to promote overall health and quality of life (WHO, 1948; Topp et. al., 2015). It further details that remote working arrangements encompass specific working conditions and organizational structures that generate psychosocial factors. These factors could potentially serve as sources or conditions that expose individuals to various biopsychosocial influences. Psychosocial factors, in turn, are closely linked to biological outcomes, potentially impacting health, illness, and the development of diseases.
2. **Caring Responsibilities:** The factor was originally suggested by Task 1.4 and Task 1.3 under the term - 'household dynamics-related burdens.' Upon subsequent discussions, the term 'caring responsibilities' was decided due to its neutral phrasing, aligning it with the criteria of defining factors.

The factor, as defined in D1.3, captures responsibilities including housework, childcare, and care for elderly, relatives, among others.

3. **Social Cohesion:** The factor was originally suggested by Task 1.4, as social network, and pertained more to workplace support networks. Upon subsequent discussions, the workplace component was isolated from the factor (termed as workplace loneliness, defined below) and was defined neutrally as the presence or absence of social ties or social support networks, referring both to physical and digital ties. This factor has potential implications for individual well-being, mental health, loneliness and productivity.

3.2.2.3 Economic impacts

Economic impacts capture the effects of RWA on economic productivity and opportunities of employees as well as factors characterising the economic productivity of regions as a whole. Economic impacts include employee productivity, access to labour markets, and local/regional economic development. These are described below.

1. **Employee Productivity:** The factor was originally suggested by Task 1.3 as ‘work intensity and productivity balance’ and during subsequent discussions separated into ‘employee productivity’ and ‘work life balance’. As suggested by Task 1.4, the factor could be realized at two levels – micro- (individual level) and meso-level (organizational level). While at an individual level, the factor refers to how efficiently and effectively a worker or a group of workers contributes to accomplishing organizational goals, at a meso-level the factor means the achievement of goals by a particular organization.
2. **Access to Labour Market:** The factor was suggested during the co-design workshop and was voted as having a significant impact. The factor was defined as access to a diverse and competitive labour force from an employer’s perspective. It also has relevance for employees, who have a wider range of possibilities of getting a job because of RWAs. The factor also captures labour participation at a societal level - participation of disabled people and inclusiveness. The dynamics of the labour market, including changes in demand for new jobs, also form a part of this factor.
3. **Local/ Regional Economic Development:** The factor was suggested by Tasks 1.1 and 1.4 during follow-up discussions on factor definitions and could be understood as the economic development of a region through which it can improve its economic, political, and social welfare state. As reported in D1.4, remote work fosters regional development by decentralising economic activities and establishing work centres in non-metropolitan areas. Areas with higher remote job shares show greater employment resilience, supporting local economies through stable spending and economic growth, particularly in smaller cities.

3.2.2.4 Socio-economic impacts

Given the interconnection between social and economic factors, the study also distinguished four socio-economic impacts. They capture impacts at the interface of social and economic conditions of employees and include work-life balance, workplace loneliness, cost of living, and tourist/ digital nomad living space demand. These are described below:

1. **Work-life Balance:** The factor was originally suggested by Task 1.3 as ‘work intensity and productivity balance’ and during subsequent discussions separated into ‘work-life balance’ and ‘employee productivity.’ D1.3 describes ‘work-life balance’ as the ability to balance between professional responsibilities and personal life - as time management and boundary settings between work and personal life, and its impact on family and social life. It is understood that work-life balance involves not only time management but also workload-related flexibility when needed. There are two key interfaces: a work-related supportive side and a life-related supportive side, each including various supportive services.
2. **Workplace Loneliness:** The factor was suggested by Task 1.3 and was separated from ‘loneliness’ in general and personal social ties as captured by the factor ‘social cohesion.’ Defined in Del.1.3, workplace loneliness is characterized by a lack of information quality, supportive leadership, supportive conditions for job demands, and individual psychological states. It is understood that as new ways of working evolve, the definition of the "workplace" is also changing. Employee services related to these "new workplace" aspects play a critical role in supporting job engagement, task completion, and providing network support when needed.
3. **Cost of Living:** Originally Task 1.1 suggested the factor ‘cost of living’, the factor ‘housing affordability’ was suggested during the codesign workshop and eventually the two were assimilated into ‘cost of living’ as it was considered more holistic. The factor can be broadly defined as the amount of money that a person needs to pay for basic needs such as food, shelter, and energy.
4. **Tourist/ Digital Nomad Living Space Demand:** Task 1.4 suggested the factor ‘local tourism economy’ originally, however, it was not adjudged as amongst the most significant factors during the co-design workshop. During subsequent discussions, the impact on tourism, specifically from digital nomads, was highlighted as a relevant dimension to be included by multiple partners. Therefore, the factor was added to cover the demand for living space from the increased number of tourists and digital nomads.

3.3 The R-Map model

In this section, the final conceptual R-Map model is presented. The elaboration of the network of causal relations between the various impacts of RWA that built the core of the R-Map model, was done in two steps during the co-design process in parallel to the identification of RWA impacts presented above: the first draft causal network of the R-Map model was developed during the co-design workshop at the UT. Further refinement and validation of the R-Map model were done throughout the series of technical workshops and

intermediate tasks fulfilled by the partners. Key information for the latter was the partner survey on cause-effect relations conducted between the second and third technical workshops.

Below, first, the results of the partner survey are presented and discussed. Then the final R-Map model is elaborated. To determine causal relations between factors the R-Map partners were asked in the survey to provide their view on (i) the existence of causal relations between two specific factors, (ii) the strength of the causal relations, (iii) the type of causal relations, and (iv) the temporality of the relationship (see section 3.3.3). Results from the analysis of causal relations between factors help in the semi-quantification of the R-Map model (see section 3.3.2)

3.3.1 Degree of Consensus on Causal Relationships

Figure 11 shows the results of the first question of the survey which was - does Factor A cause a change in Factor B, with the option of answering 'yes', 'no' or 'I don't know'. We associate a value of 1 with each 'yes' mentioned and sum the values per causal relationship to arrive at the heatmap. The heatmap representation captures the directional graph with the y-axis depicting the factors where a link emanates from and the x-axis depicting a factor where it terminates. Due to its directional nature, the heatmap is not symmetric along the diagonal. Three classifications – high (values 9 and 10), medium (values 6 to 8) and low (values less than 6) consensus – were made based on quantiles, such that the number of values in each class is approximately the same.

Figure 11: Degree of consensus on causal relationships

The identification of the direction of links reveals a strong consensus on the effect of RWA on several impact factors, specifically, health and wellbeing, mobility pattern, multilocality, polycentricity, social cohesion, tourist/digital nomad living space, work-life balance, workplace loneliness, access to labour market, and local/regional economic development. Additionally, there is significant agreement on the influence of various social and socioeconomic factors on health and well-being—such as social cohesion, work-life balance, workplace loneliness, caring responsibilities, cost of living, and access to local amenities—establishing health and well-being as a broader, final impact beyond immediate outcomes.

Both digital infrastructure and transport accessibility are seen as key drivers for RWA by all partners. Furthermore, multilocality and polycentricity are identified as critical bridges across domains, influencing a wide range of factors. There is strong agreement that polycentricity impacts spatial factors such as land consumption and mobility patterns, as well as economic factors such as access to the labour market and local/regional economic development. Similarly, there is broad consensus that multilocality is connected to the spatial factor of polycentricity and the economic factor of local/regional economic development. High

agreement also exists on the role of digital infrastructure accessibility as a key driver of mobility patterns and polycentricity, a relationship further clarified through the introduction of the factor of relocation.

3.3.2 Strength of Causal Relationships

A high consensus among partners of a causal relation between single impacts or driving factors does not allow to make any conclusions on the strengths of this relation. Therefore, in the second question of the survey we asked about the strength of a given relationship between Factor A and B, with the possibility of answering 'weak', 'medium', 'strong' or 'I don't know'. A weight of 1, 2 and 3 was associated respectively with the answers 'weak', 'medium' and 'strong' and was summed per causal relationship to arrive at the heatmap. Also, if respondents replied 'yes' in the previous question and specify 'I don't know' in the second question, we also assign a weight of 1. We use the quantile criteria here as well, to specify five categories, including very strong (values 23 to 25), strong (values 19 to 22), medium (values 17 and 18), weak (values 11 to 16) and very weak (values less than 11). The results are depicted in the same format as above in Figure 12.

Most important findings are that RWA have the strongest causal relations with the impacts: health and wellbeing, work life balance, workplace loneliness, and access to labour markets. They are further also strongly related to the impacts of mobility patterns, polycentricity, tourist living space demand, and employee productivity. Another interesting finding is that social cohesion is a weakly linked to RWA despite the strong consensus of the relation elicited in the figure below.

Figure 12: Strength of causal relationships

Most important findings are that RWA have the strongest causal relations with the impacts: health and wellbeing, work life balance, workplace loneliness, and access to labour markets. They are further also strongly related to the impacts of mobility patterns, polycentricity, tourist living space demand, and employee productivity. Another interesting finding is that social cohesion is weakly linked to RWA despite the strong consensus of the relation elicited in the figure above.

Other very strong causal relations elicited by the partners are health and wellbeing on employee productivity, and polycentricity on mobility patterns, social cohesion, work life balance, workplace loneliness. The driver access to local amenities strongly correlates with health and wellbeing, and the driver digital infrastructure accessibility with access to labour markets. Overall, health and wellbeing is the factor that is strongly affected by a number of impacts, which makes this factor a key final impact of the R-Map model. Also, the factor carbon emissions is affected by 8 other impacts though often only mapped as a weak link. This is potentially because the factor carbon emissions was added a little later in the process to the set of factors, and so/thus not all partners had assessed causal relations to it in the survey.

3.3.3 Type of Causal Relationships

For developing the R-Map model it was crucial to assess whether the mapped causal relations between factors are positive or negative. To address this issue the partners had to assess the type of causal relationships between two factors by answering the question whether an increase of factor A causes an increase or a decrease of factor B, with the possibility of answering 'yes', 'no', or 'I don't know'. Partners were also allowed to enter 'mixed' in the comments if they believed that the relationship varies depending on the context. For broad, container factor terms, an additional step was undertaken to refine their definitions and to clarify what constitutes an increase or decrease in the respective factors. Specifically, this refinement was applied to the following factors:

1. Mobility Pattern: The scope was narrowed to focus specifically on the usage of public transport.
2. Taxation, Social Security, and Insurance Regulations: The definition was streamlined to address tax benefits associated with remote working.

The results are shown below in Figure 13. All mapped causal relations are shown on the y-axis with length of the bar chart indicating the number of partners having assessed the relation and in colour the results of the assessment per partner (green= positive relation, red=negative relation, beige=I don't know). The figure further shows the degree of consensus among partners on the type of relation: the longer the green or red colour per bar, the higher the degree of consensus. In case of shorter bars, not all partners assessed the causal relationship to/that exist.

Figure 13: Type of causal relationships – positive, negative or mixed

Overall, a large number of relationships is conclusively positive. The highest degree of consensus exists on the positive relation of work-life balance, social cohesion, and access to local amenities, with health and wellbeing. High consensus exists also on the positive relations between multilocality and polycentricity, health and wellbeing and employee productivity, and digital infrastructure accessibility and RWA. For several other relations, some partner did not confirm the positivity of the relations which might have to do with their scientific background and knowledge.

Overall, 10 of the mapped relations are assessed by the partners as conclusively negative. The highest consensus exists on the relation of workplace loneliness to health and wellbeing, and caring responsibilities to work-life balance. In total, 14 relations got a mixed assessment by the partners. Reasons for this differential view on relations can be the varying experiential knowledge and experience of partners with respect to the relations, different mental models of contexts these relations are applied to by partners, and varying interpretations of factors by partners. The latter is potentially aggravated by the purposely broad definition of factors that in some cases serve as container terms for more than one concrete impact indicator. For the overall R-Map model developed in this task the relations are to be excluded from the model, given the uninformative prior in such cases within the Bayesian setup may produce uncertain results. For the application of the model in different contexts and regions in WP4 of the R-Map project these relations will have to be re-examined.

3.3.4 Temporality of Causal Relationships

Finally, the temporality of the mapped causal relations was assessed by the partners in answering the questions of how long a relation between factor A and factor B takes to realise. The distinction between factor relations at a temporal scale is crucial for eliciting cause-effect chains over several factors from the here-assessed 1 to 1 relations.

The results of the question are visualised in Figure 14, distinguishing causal relations into the categories of short, medium, and long-term. This temporality is mapped on the x-axis with drivers being plotted on the very left and long-term effects of RWA being plotted on the far right of the graph.

Figure 14: Relative temporality of causal relationships

It is important to mention that the temporality of the relations is mapped in Figure 14 in relative, not absolute terms. Temporality should further be understood in terms of the domain, i.e. spatial impacts may take longer to be realised, than impacts in the social domain. For example, health and well-being, identified as a medium-term impact and positioned one step beyond immediate effects such as workplace loneliness and work-life balance, is manifested considerably sooner than polycentricity.

Additionally, the final assessment presented in Figure 14 is evaluated relative to RWAs and other associated impacts. For instance, while the majority of partners indicated that the causal relationship between RWAs and polycentricity unfolds over the long term, a similar time frame was identified for the relationship between polycentricity and land consumption. Consequently, in relation to RWAs and land consumption, polycentricity is classified as a medium-term impact.

Overall, we can conclude that the partner survey provided valuable insights for the analysis of causal relations between factors that help with the conceptual design of the R-Map model and its semi-quantification. For the

co-design process we can constitute that the results of the survey rather confirmed the initial mapping of relations done during the co-design workshop at the UT. Moreover, a large degree of agreement between partners exists regarding the causal relations between impacts of RWA. Nevertheless, a high agreement does not necessarily translate into a strong causal relationship, which underlines the quality of the survey for developing the R-Map model.

3.3.5 The Conceptual R-Map Model

Based on the results of the partner survey on the consensus of causal relations between factors and their respective strengths, certain links of low relevance were excluded from the R-Map model. The criteria for retaining or omitting links in the R-Map model were as follows:

1. Exclusion of very weak links: Links identified as very weak, based on survey responses regarding the strength of causal relationships (Figure 12), were omitted. For example, links such as multilocality to employee productivity and work-life balance to workplace loneliness were excluded under this criterion.
2. Exclusion of redundant links: Links that are redundant due to being already captured by another causal chain were removed. For instance, the link between caring responsibilities and employee productivity was excluded, as it was determined to be mediated by work-life balance.
3. Minimizing loops: To ensure clarity and facilitate modelling in Task 2.2 as Bayesian Belief Networks, loops were excluded wherever possible. In cases of two-way relationships, the dominant direction was retained. For example, while a bidirectional relationship was identified between cost of living and tourist/digital nomad living space demand, the link from cost of living to demand was weak, whereas the reverse direction was strong. Therefore, the link from "tourist/digital nomad living space demand" to "cost of living" was retained, and the reverse link was excluded.
4. Focus on RWA-driven causal changes: As mentioned, links mediated by RWAs were prioritized in the conceptual model to emphasize causal changes driven by remote work, aiding discussions on this theme. For instance, while strong connections were identified between access to local amenities and digital infrastructure accessibility, these were temporarily excluded.
5. Exclusion of mixed relationships for modelling in Task 2.2: Links characterized by mixed relationships (Figure 13), while retained in the conceptual R-Map model, will be excluded from the modelling exercise in Task 2.2.

After semi-quantifying the causal relationships between factors and classifying them, a directed network was generated, resulting in the conceptual R-Map model presented in Figures 15 and 16. To facilitate focused discussions, a simplified representation was adopted, wherein all causal links from drivers to impacts were mediated through RWAs. This approach emphasizes the scope of the task, which is limited to understanding causal relationships stemming from RWAs. While direct relationships between drivers and impacts are of

interest and may be utilized in Task 2.2, the primary objective of Task 2.1 was to map causal relationships emanating from RWAs and between impact factors.

Figure 15 represents the factors as nodes and the causal relationships as directed arrows, with their weights reflecting the strength of relationships as indicated by partners in the survey. Arrows associated with carbon emissions have been moved to a class above the one indicated in the survey, to correct for the later inclusion and subsequent underrepresentation in the survey. It can be seen in Figure 15 that the factors of health and wellbeing, cost of living, and regional economy are the key final impacts of remote working arrangements, indicated by a high number of incoming (receiving) links. Further, it can be observed that spatial impacts are rather intermediate impacts resulting in social, economic and socio-economic impacts.

Figure 15: The conceptual R-Map Model (a)

Figure 16 further depicts these relationships by their type—positive, negative, or mixed. Most of the causal relationships included in the R-Map mode are positive relations, i.e. when the factor where the link starts increases also the factor where the link terminates increases. While this is not so important for the conceptual design of the R-Map model, it needs to be taken into account when it comes to the modelling of impacts and the translation of factors into indicators.

Figure 16: The conceptual R-Map Model (b)

To analyse how changes in Remote Work Arrangements (RWAs) and other drivers influence final impacts, and to assess the significance of intermediate factors in this process, specific causal chains can be isolated from the R-Map model.

Causal chains can be described as pathways of influence that originate from a root cause and lead to an impact, passing through multiple intermediate factors. A causal chain can have several causal paths. These causal chains can be used to identify confounders and mediating factors. Figure 17 illustrates an example of a causal chain from RWAs to the cost of living, highlighting the following causal paths:

1. RWA > Tourist Demand > Cost of Living
2. RWA > Relocation > Polycentricity > Cost of Living
3. RWA > Relocation > Polycentricity > Land Consumption > Cost of Living
4. RWA > Multilocality > Polycentricity > Cost of Living
5. RWA > Multilocality > Cost of Living
6. RWA > Mobility Pattern < Polycentricity > Cost of Living
7. RWA > Mobility Pattern < Multilocality > Cost of Living

Figure 17: A causal chain from RWA to cost of living in the R-Map conceptual model

In terms of factor types and their implications, we make the following few observations:

1. **Mobility Pattern as a Collider**
Mobility pattern acts as a collider or common effect in the causal chain. Controlling for it would violate the back-door criterion, resulting in spurious correlations. Therefore, it should be excluded in a multivariate regression analysis in a Bayesian setup.
2. **Multilocality as a Confounder**
Multilocality serves as a confounder between polycentricity and the cost of living. Consequently, it is critical to control this factor in the analysis to prevent biases and ensure valid causal inferences.
3. **Tourist Demand as a Mediator**
Tourist demand can be classified as a mediator in the causal chain. However, since not all tourist demand is driven by remote work and is influenced by external factors beyond the causal map, it cannot be excluded outright. A more effective approach is to introduce additional control variables to better understand their contribution to the final impact (i.e., cost of living).
4. **Relocation as a Mediator**
Similar to tourist demand, relocation can be classified as a mediator in the causal chain, and one which is not entirely driven by remote work. Therefore, it should not be excluded from the analysis. Instead, other control variables should be introduced to isolate their role in influencing the cost of living.
5. **Land Consumption as a Mediator**
Land consumption is strictly a mediator between polycentricity and the cost of living. Since land consumption can be safely assumed to be driven entirely by polycentricity, it may be excluded from the analysis if the focus is solely on understanding the impact of remote work on the cost of living. However, this exclusion should only be considered after controlling for variables that drive polycentricity.

By distinguishing between confounders, mediators, and colliders within a specific causal chain, the analysis can be structured to prevent spurious correlations, maintain valid causal pathways, and ensure a robust understanding of the relationships between RWAs, intermediate factors, and final impacts. This approach can also be extended to other causal chains, allowing for a detailed assessment of the effects of various factors on specific final impacts of interest, such as health and wellbeing, carbon emissions, employee productivity, or the regional economy.

3.4 Computational implementation of the conceptual R-Map model

The R-Map conceptual model serves as the foundation for Task 2.2, which focuses on distilling, detailing, implementing, and validating the R-Map model. Specifically, Task 2.2 involves formulating indicators and proxies which are in the form of measured data for the factors identified in Task 2.1 and harmonizing datasets as inputs for the implemented model; the datasets so far identified are outlined in the subsequent section. The implemented model will be a reduced version or subset of the conceptual model. The reason is that the

scope of the model will be constrained by the availability of relevant data and certainty of causal relationships. After the indicators are developed, the causal relationships will be reformulated using these specific indicators, ensuring alignment with the R-Map conceptual model. This step is essential, as some factors may have multiple indicators, and additional control variables may need to be introduced.

The R-Map model will be implemented with the rationale of treating the conceptual model shown in Figures 15-16 as the graph-based representation of statistical relations among factors. And the statistical relations are to be modelled using a Bayesian approach. Hence, both surveyed knowledge and measured indicators from datasets are treated to capture people's belief and actual measurements at the same time. Insights from the survey regarding the types of causal relationships can be utilized as the model priors in the Bayesian setup, while likelihoods and posterior probabilities can be derived from the data where available. This methodology also enables several analytical directions, such as assessing the significance of various factors in influencing specific outcomes (looking "up" the network) or predicting potential outcomes under hypothetical scenarios where certain factors take predefined values (looking "down" the network), as discussed in Section 2.1.4. Furthermore, the model can accommodate the addition of new factors and facilitate learning of the causal network structure.

As the R-Map model is designed as an integrated assessment framework for Europe, and most indicators are singular values at NUTS-3 or NUTS-2 levels, it is reasonable to anticipate model outputs in terms of singular values at these scales. However, as the project advances into regional case studies under WP4, more localized data can be collected, enabling detailed, context-specific analyses and/or predictions.

4. Data sources to inform the R-Map model

To perform an integrated assessment of spatial, social, and socio-economic impacts of RWA across Europe and to evaluate the impacts of remote working arrangements on different regions in WP4, the here identified factors need to be translated into measurable indicators and connected to data sets that inform these indicators for the different spatial units. This part of the work is conducted in Task 2.2 of the WP2. To prepare for this, Task 2.1 identifies suitable data sources that allow to inform the indicators of the R-Map model. Possible data sources for this are publicly available data sets published on open data portals including other HEU projects that publish open data sets as results of their research, data that is derived from the large-scale survey conducted in the R-Map project (Task 1.5), and unconventional data sources, for example data potentially derived from social media platforms such as LinkedIn or Twitter (now X). Suitable data sets from these different sources to inform factors in the R-Map model are discussed in this chapter.

To inform the R-Map model factors and indicators the data sets need to fulfil certain requirements. The following criteria were applied for selecting the data sets discussed below.

- The data needs to be publicly available and accessible
- The data needs to be available for different years to allow the analyses of changes over time (e.g. before and after the COVID-19 pandemic)
- The data needs to be available at a sufficient spatial resolution. As the goal of the R-Map project is to assess the impacts of RWA at the regional level, the data is ideally available at NUTS3-level or NUTS2-level.
- The data needs to be available - ideally - for the entire EU to support a coherent and consistent assessment of RWA impacts across different case studies.

4.1 Open data sources

Open data sources provide access to publicly available data sets typically compiled and verified by governmental authorities. The following publicly available data sets are suitable to inform the R-Map model.

Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/en/web/main/data>), the statistical office of the European Union, provide high-quality statistics and data on Europe for a large variety of different topics and themes, including land use, economy, population and social conditions, transport, environment, among many other topics. Eurostat data is harmonized across all EU countries, available for longer time series, and provided at a high spatial resolution down to NUTS3 level, which makes it a rich and important data source for the R-Map Model.

The European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound) provides data and surveys on working conditions and sustainable work, industrial relations, labour market change and quality and life and public services in Europe (<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/data>). The data offers a unique source of comparative information on the quality of living and working conditions across the EU and this is very valuable to inform the R-Map model. Several surveys that Eurofound conducts are done repeatedly and allow for the analysis of changes over time. The spatial resolution is often limited to country level, more detailed resolution needs to be checked and requested for single data sets.

OpenStreetMap (OSM) is an online open geographic database, regularly updated and provides detailed spatial data across the world maintained by a community of volunteers via open collaboration. While this spatial data cannot be directly used to inform specific factors or indicators of the R-Map model, it can be used to construct indicators. Examples are for instance a spatial data layer of road networks across Europe provided at <https://www.globio.info/download-grip-dataset> that can be helpful for assessing transport accessibility per region, or a spatial data set containing points of interest that might help assess the density of amenities per region in Europe.

The EU Social Progress Index (EU-SPI, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/assets/social-progress/index.html#/) provides data for EU regions on a range of social and environmental aspects. The data sets include data on basic needs (housing, medical care) and foundations of wellbeing (information and communication, health) including environmental quality. They are available at NUTS2 level for the years 2016, 2020, and 2024 which makes it suitable to compare the situation before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

The ESPON Data and Knowledge Portal (<https://gis-portal.espon.eu/arcgis/apps/sites/#/espon-hub>) provides data and indicators on European territorial development including a broad variety of topics such as population and living conditions, economy and labour markets, employment, transport and accessibility, among other topics. The data is publicly available at NUTS2 resp. NUTS3 level for different years, covering the entire EU territory.

The ESPON data portal also provides several highly aggregated indices composed of available data. That might serve to inform single R-Map indicators. The good life enabler index is for instance compiled of indicators that are partly also included in the R-Map model. The documentation of the construction of the index might serve as a good basis for targeting suitable data sets to be included in the R-Map model (<https://archive.espon.eu/sites/default/files/attachments/ESPON%20Working%20Paper%2C%20Is%20Our%20Life%20Good%20Enough.pdf>)

Figure 18: The framework for good life enabler index (source: ESPON 2021)

Europe-wide data sets that are produced and made publicly available in the context of other HEU projects might be also relevant data sources to inform indicators of the R-Map model. For instance, the LOCALISED project (<https://www.localised-project.eu/>), which aims at downscaling decarbonisation trajectories consistent with the EU's net-zero targets to local levels, has published an open data set via a data sharing API on Github that contains also small-scaled sociodemographic and socioeconomic data as well as data on industries and services <https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/LOCALISED-Datasharing-API-Client>. Most of the data, that originally stems from public data portals such as Eurostat etc, has been downscaled and disaggregated from a broader spatial resolution to NUTS3 and even Local Area Units (LAU), which increases the relevance of the data of the R-Map project.

4.2 Large-Scale Survey on Remote Workers’ Perceptions, Requirements, and Location Choices (WP1, task 1.5)

In WP1, as part of/in Task 1.5 of the R-Map project a large-scale survey was conducted to collect primary data on remote workers' perceptions, requirements, and factors influencing location choices. The survey aimed to create a comprehensive dataset by targeting approximately 20,000 participants, which could inform

subsequent stages of the project. Initially, the survey focused on European participants; however, due to limited responses, it was expanded to include similar countries such as the United States, Canada, and Australia.

The questionnaire captured various aspects of remote work, including hours worked remotely per week, industry background, gender, workplace preferences and drivers, commuting distances and modes, as well as participants' current work and home location (municipality level). It also inquired whether respondents had relocated their place of work or residence due to remote work and, if so, the corresponding municipalities before and after the change. To ensure data privacy, participants were anonymized. Respondents were asked to provide municipality names in a textual format. However, this introduced challenges with data consistency, requiring substantial data cleaning efforts.

4.2.1 Data Processing and Matching

To associate municipalities with spatial administrative boundaries, a two-pronged strategy was employed:

1. For European municipalities, responses were matched with Local Area Units (LAUs) and linked to their respective NUTS-3 regions.
2. For non-European municipalities, responses were matched with GADM (the Database of Global Administrative Areas).

Furthermore, municipalities were classified into urban-rural categories for proceeding tasks and dissemination purposes. For Europe, the NUTS-3 typology was used, classifying regions as predominantly urban, predominantly rural, or intermediate. For non-European municipalities, the Degree of Urbanisation framework was applied (The European Commission & United Nations Human Settlements Programme, 2021), categorizing level 2 administrative areas (approximating municipal scales) into categories such as urban centres, dense urban clusters, semi-dense urban clusters, suburban or peri-urban, rural cluster, low-density rural, very low-density rural, and water.

4.2.2 Insights and Inputs for Task 2.2

The results of this large-scale survey are potentially a rich data set to inform the quantification of indicators for the R-Map model (Task 2.2), particularly as such a survey was never done before. The data set can especially help explore some of the following key research questions:

1. Relocation due to remote work: Assessing the extent to which remote work influences residential relocation and its relationship with hours worked remotely.
2. Distance of relocation: Determining how far individuals are willing to relocate from their workplace based on the extent of remote work.
3. Job location choices: Exploring whether individuals are willing to secure jobs farther from their homes and how this correlates with remote working hours.
4. Regional attractiveness: Evaluating the ability of regions to retain or attract remote workers.

5. Commuting behaviour: Analysing commuting mode choices in relation to commuting distances and transport accessibility.

These inquiries can be further enriched by integrating other open datasets mentioned previously, allowing for an investigation into factors such as access to amenities, transport accessibility, digital infrastructure availability, and taxation in shaping relocation decisions. Additionally, this data can be used to assess whether relocation results in actual land consumption, leveraging built-up area data from sources such as the Global Human Settlement (GHS) dataset. This dataset provides a unique foundation for advancing understanding of remote work's spatial and socio-economic impacts, offering critical insights for policy and planning.

4.2.3 Insights from LinkedIn Poll on Remote Work Preferences and Impacts

Complementary to the large-scale survey, a LinkedIn poll was conducted by the R-Map project, garnering approximately 5,500 responses. This poll sought to further explore the workplace and location preferences of remote workers, as well as the perceived impacts of remote work on productivity and job satisfaction. Key findings from the poll include:

1. Positive impact on productivity: Respondents overwhelmingly reported that remote work had a positive effect on their productivity.
2. Enhanced job satisfaction: An even stronger positive response was observed regarding the impact of remote work on job satisfaction.
3. Preference for suburban or rural living: A significant preference emerged for suburban or rural areas over urban areas, indicating a tendency towards less densely populated living environments.
4. Flexibility in work schedules and location: Respondents expressed a positive sentiment toward the flexibility remote work offers in terms of choosing work schedules and locations.
5. Varied support preferences: Opinions varied on the type of support deemed beneficial for remote working, with preferences ranging from ergonomic office supplies to mental health and wellness initiatives.

These insights underscore the importance of employee productivity and health and well-being as key final impact factors. Additionally, the preference for less densely populated areas reflects a centrifugal shift away from urban centres, highlighting the evolving spatial dynamics associated with remote work.

4.3 Unconventional Data Sources

To complement traditional datasets, we explored the potential of leveraging unconventional data sources to inform key factors included in the R-Map model. This included examining the data policies of social media platforms such as X (formerly known as Twitter), LinkedIn, and Threads, as well as open datasets shared within developer communities on platforms like Kaggle. Additionally, other sources offering transport, movement, walkability, and cost-of-living data at urban or regional scales were also considered.

4.3.1 Social Media Platforms and Open Data Repositories

1. X (formerly Twitter): Previously, X provided free access to its API and geolocated tweet collection, enabling sentiment analysis, and topic and keyword modelling (Saura et al., 2022), which could offer insights into public perceptions of remote work. However, these services have transitioned to a paid model, limiting their accessibility for research purposes.
2. LinkedIn: As a platform rich in data on job postings and trends related to remote work, LinkedIn could have been a valuable resource. However, its free API services have been discontinued, restricting open access to such information.
3. Threads (Meta): Threads, a newer social media platform similar to X, still allows limited free API usage. Although its user base is smaller compared to X, it remains a potential avenue for sentiment analysis and other exploratory studies.
4. Kaggle: Kaggle hosts various developer-contributed datasets, including historical tweets and job postings in specific industries. While these datasets provide an opportunity to examine certain trends, their reliability and comprehensiveness remain, like for other social media data, uncertain, especially for nuanced analyses like assessing the spatial or economic impacts of remote work.

4.3.2 Other Unconventional Data Sources

We also investigated platforms providing urban and regional-scale data on transport, movement patterns, walkability, and cost of living. For instance:

1. Google Maps API: Previously a viable option for accessing Points of Interest (POI) data, this has also shifted to a paid service, limiting its feasibility for large-scale, cost-effective research.
2. Mobile Phone Data: Aggregated and anonymized data from European Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) provides insights into stationary points and flows using unique identifiers linked to location and timestamps. Despite its utility, access is restricted and typically available only for specific studies under GDPR-compliant frameworks.
3. Mobility Data Repositories: Mobility data at the national and European levels presents a valuable resource for analyzing transport and movement patterns. National initiatives include Germany's Mobility Data Space, the Netherlands' iSHARE, and France's Bison Futé. The European Mobility Data Space (EMDS) initiative provides a unified framework for data interoperability and sharing in the mobility and transport sectors. Supported by the deployEMDS project under the EU Digital Europe Programme, EMDS facilitates multimodal mobility, traffic management, and sustainable urban mobility assessments, building on the groundwork of PrepDSpace4Mobility. However, the project will be fully operational only by 2026, requiring reliance on national repositories in the interim. City-level datasets include specific datasets, such as UTD19 curated by the Institute for Transport Planning and Systems at ETH Zurich, which provide detailed traffic flow data at the city level.

4. Remote Sensing Data: Satellite-based remote sensing data, particularly nighttime imagery from SDGSAT-1, offers the potential for detecting traffic volumes and analyzing urban mobility patterns. SDGSAT-1 is accessible for scientific purposes, making it a promising resource for mobility studies. However, its temporal coverage poses a challenge for continuous or high-frequency analysis, limiting its ability to capture dynamic trends comprehensively.
5. Property and Job Listings Data: Web scraping of property websites and job listing platforms offers insights into housing and commercial property trends, relocation patterns, market demand, and remote work-related roles. However, legal and ethical considerations must be addressed to comply with data usage policies, and data cleaning is required to handle inconsistencies across platforms.
6. Other data sources:
 - Walkability Indices: Open sources like Walk Score provide valuable data on walkability, which can inform indicators related to access to local amenities.
 - Quality of Life Metrics: Studies such as the "Regional Quality of Living in Europe" (Lagas et al. 2015) offer insights into regional quality of life metrics, which can inform indicators related to cost of living.

While unconventional datasets provide unique insights into mobility patterns, housing markets, and employment trends, they come with challenges such as limited access, temporal coverage gaps, and data compliance requirements. Despite these hurdles, integrating these datasets with traditional sources can significantly enhance our understanding of the spatial and socio-economic impacts of remote work. Future efforts should focus on overcoming access barriers, fostering partnerships, and ensuring data quality to maximize their potential.

5. Reflections on the R-Map model

In developing the R-Map model for the integrated assessment of impacts resulting from RWA, it was essential to keep the scope of the model manageable without significantly compromising the number of key factors influencing remote working or being impacted by the same. The implemented co-design approach proved to help capture the rich and diverse experiential knowledge of the involved partners, advisory board members and domain experts and merge it with the comprehensive insights from literature and expert interviews collected in WP1. To make the conceptual R-Map model concrete and the co-design process a success, a methodological approach and terminology adopted from participatory systems mapping exercises were introduced. In the following, we reflect on the relevance, value and validity of the conceptual R-Map model but also on its limitations and constraints.

5.1 Relevance value and validity of the R-Map model

To avoid misconceptions about the purpose and the making of the R-Map model, it is imperative to consider the "doubly-complex" nature of the phenomenon that it aims to model. Furthermore, it is critically important to note that it is not only meant to be "a model of" a phenomenon but "a model for" contemplating our interferences with and our situation concerning a phenomenon. In other words, we are not aiming to make a replica of a large geographical system to predict its behaviour over time but rather aiming to explicate a collective understanding of the inner workings and mechanisms underlying some complex and intertwined chains of causes and effects in such a way as to get a grip on how our policies and arrangements may help or hamper our abilities to steer such complex dynamics of change. The double complexity label is borrowed from Portugali (2011) in reference to complex phenomena that are not only complex from a geographical (spatial, temporal, social) point of view but also from an anthropogenic dynamics stance brought about by political aspirations, visions, and decisions of governance and planning bodies. In other words, here we are not only dealing with getting a grip on "how things change" but also on "how to change things". Simply put, the model cannot possibly satisfy those who seek an accurate and comprehensive (scientific) large-scale impact assessment model, nor will it satisfy those who are looking for easy-to-remember lessons or catchy conclusions for policy development in the form of linear rules of thumb.

Thus, our modelling endeavour is based on a stance in between these two extremes, i.e. the geographical modelling science and policy analysis. The main goal of this task is to consolidate "a model architecture" for a BBN in task 2.2 that can be reasonably traced back and justified concerning the findings of the partners from the literature as well as their experiential knowledge and expert intuition about the pertinence of the factors and their causal connections to one another. As far as expert opinions and literature findings are concerned, the partners from the sister project WinWin4WorkLife, who were invited as peers to our meetings to double-check our findings, confirmed that the resultant model architecture and its constituent factors conform to their findings and expert intuitions. However, to attain the ultimate objective of obtaining a common understanding of the urban/rural divide, we need to work towards the completion of Tasks 2.3 and 2.4, before which any insight will be inconclusive by nature. For the time being, the model architecture produced in this task should be regarded as a minimal picture of the most relevant factors to be studied across the various regions within the scope of the project. The eventual utility (or futility) of the model for policy analysis can only be judged empirically (validated or falsified) once it is quantified and contextualized to provide the possibility of zooming in and out of regions (from NUTS3 and NUTS2 to NUTS1 level). The quantitative consistency of the model in terms of geospatial (zonal) statistics in these zooming in and out operations

(respectively regarded as disaggregation and aggregation processes) can also only be verified once Tasks 2.2 and 2.3 are completed.

However, from a qualitative level, the model as it is right now can be expected to be a useful representation of a collective systemic understanding of a complicated matter (a doubly complex system), i.e. the compound impacts of remote working arrangements and the way through which multiple short-term and mid-term effects of RWA at disaggregated geospatial resolutions (local phenomena) seem to lead to longer-term and more aggregate impacts (global issues). In that sense, the model architecture per se can be already used as a reflective device for policy analysis and deliberations in participatory or democratic decision-making processes.

5.2 Limitations of the R-Map model

We acknowledge several important theoretical and practical limitations of the R-Map model that cannot be simply addressed by mere larger investments in time and effort, but rather those require a different approach or different studies altogether. The first limitation is of a theoretical and methodological nature resulting from the inherent inadequacy of reliance on the collective intuition of a group of experts for understanding or mapping all relevant factors of influence and impact. Even if the scope of the R-Map model was to be confined to a single domain perspective such as the economic impacts of remote working, a much deeper approach would be required to address the entirety of the subject; let alone the difficulty of collating the various sorts of impact factors at inherently incommensurate spatial or temporal scales or social bearings. Thus, instead of the disciplinary representativeness or adequacy of the model, its integrality is claimed in two senses: the multi-disciplinary integration of views and the operational integration potential of the model in participatory policy development cycles. The second limitation of the model mainly arises out of the incompatibility and incommensurability of the spatial and temporal scales of analysis and the definition of the indices on the one hand and the contextual impertinence of the indices when used in atypical social and political/administrative contexts other than those typically considered as globally frequent or pertinent.

It is important to distinguish the nature of the proposed R-Map model from the widely known and sought-after regression models (linear, polynomial, or non-linear ANN-based regression models). Regression models are typically built to replicate the input-output relationship of functions (assuming that a function as a system with known inputs and outputs can be meaningfully conceptualized). However, here the very scope of the system and the nature of the connections is what we are after in the first place. Linear regression models have been historically popular as they quench the desire of humans to capture simple relationships between variables in the form of "the less of this the more of that" or "the more of this the more of that" types of rules of thumb. However, aiming for making any such "closed form" model would inevitably reduce and oversimplify the architecture of the model prematurely. In fact, in Task 2.1 we have focused solely on the conceptual design of the R-Map model, seeking to ensure that we are aiming to model a relevant set of relationships, regardless of whether they can be simplified or reduced to linear or non-linear relationships.

In practical terms, we will proceed with quantifying a chosen set of relationships as conditional probability links in Task 2.2. Therefore, the R-Map model produced at this stage should not be yet considered as any kind of a predictive model in a quantitative sense but rather as a qualitative apparatus for collectively reflecting on the complex set of relationships between factors of importance and interest related to the remote working arrangements in Europe.

In other words, the model architecture per se can be judged here in terms of its inherent limitations being related to the impossibility of ensuring a complete (diverse and inclusive) representation of stakeholders and their views in two important steps: 1) defining what factors must be included in the model architecture (the nodes), and 2) defining what links (causal relations) need to be modelled (to be eventually quantified) in the model. In the absence of a presumably perfect or complete benchmark, we are effectively settling for a rather pragmatic approach to the consolidation of the conceptual model. We firstly relied on the reports made by the consortium partners in WP1 (which are based on a wide literature review) to curate a set of potentially relevant factors to be included in the model; asked the partners to help us sift through the list of potentially relevant factors to pick a handful of more relevant ones; contemplated together with the consortium partners on which links are the most important ones to be modelled; and out of those links we chose a handful of the least ambiguous ones.

There are still more limitations and challenges awaiting the next step of our modelling endeavour, which is about quantifying the conditional probabilities in the BBN model. Most of these limitations are related to the unavailability of reliable indices or proxy indicators at commensurate and compatible scales for a wide-range geographical analysis. However, as indicated earlier, the R-Map model at this stage is merely the rough model architecture (the set of topological relationships within the variables in the model). The next step to be taken immediately afterwards to address these limitations is about exacting the definition of the variables or factors in the model and choosing reliable and compatible data sources such as indices or proxy indicators that can be unambiguously reproduced for the entire geographical scope of the model at least for two temporal snapshots before and after the COVID-19 pandemic so that a sense of causality can be established and tested with the quantified (trained) model in the next step (Task 2.2).

The most important theoretical limitation that seems to be infeasible to overcome within the timeframe of the project is that the complex architecture of the model brings about the reasonable expectation that the emergence of impact at mid-term to long-term horizons can be somehow simulated with such a network model architecture, and yet the unavailability of data at different (relevant) time series on the one hand (concerning quantitative model validation and calibration) and the impracticality of iterating through epochs or passes through the BBN network means that we should eventually settle for a "before and after" temporal snapshot analysis rather than any kind of longitudinal simulation-like analysis.

Finally, we need to acknowledge that the conceptual R-Map model does not fully avoid the risk of ecological fallacy when being implemented. We can conclude from the co-design exercise with a certain security and accuracy that certain impacts might occur as a causal effect of RWA, but we cannot claim fully that the impact would occur at all if there were no RWA arrangements in place. This degree of uncertainty will always need to be communicated in the context of the application of the R-Map model.

5.3 Disclaimer: What is the R-Map model and what is it not?

In the absolute sense of the term, "*all models are wrong, but some models can be useful*" (a reworded version of the famous quote from George Box, the social scientist). The R-Map model is no exception to this rule. Hence, there is absolutely no point in pretending to have built a Crystal Ball or an accurate model of the effects and the aggregate impacts of Remote Working Arrangements on the economy, society, and environment (mediated mostly through the so-called spatial effects of remote working). Instead, the R-Map model and its usefulness need to be validated as to its purpose for being a decision support tool for Participatory Policy

Evaluation (PPE). Up to this point, we have focused on capturing the collective understanding (based on insights produced in WP 1) of the project partners, advisory board members and invited experts as a de-facto group of experts of the existing systemic and causal relationships between factors that are somehow related to the remote working arrangements (RWA), from the most immediate and disaggregated effects to the mediators and the ultimate and aggregate impact factors of the changes in the society, economy, and environment. In this sense, the full potential of our approach is yet to be tested in scaling up participatory system modelling workshops. Even though conducting such mass-scale participatory modelling workshops falls beyond the scope of the current project, the idea of scalability is still part of the ethos of our modelling approach. Since the beginning of the modelling process, we did not have the illusion that such complex and systemic relationships could be possibly captured into any able regression-based model. For a regression model based on a frequentist understanding of probabilities, it would be inherently incapable of capturing the insights of the participating experts into the model. Besides, even if successful in terms of making predictions in an ex-post assessment setting, a regression-based model would be inherently incapable of explaining the mechanisms that underpin the complex socio-geographical (i.e. multi-level and multi-dimensional) dynamics of changes and impacts of RWA.

Thus, we aimed at making a model as a reflective medium by which a group of experts or potentially a much larger group of stakeholders can share and delineate their collective understanding of how one driver or factor leads to another to impact our living environment in their social, spatial, economic or socio-economic aspects. However, this collective understanding of the causal directional linkages between the factors cannot be mistaken for the "true" way in which these factors relate to one another, for it is clear that our collective understanding of the world, no matter how large our collective, cannot be assumed to represent the objective truth (rhetorically speaking).

Therefore, we can humbly divert our attention away from a one-to-one representation or replication of the dynamics of change to the potential usefulness of the model for policy analysis and policy development.

The model as a predictive tool will be almost certainly wrong in one way or another, but it can be a useful medium for collectively reflecting on the efficacy of our public and private policies surrounding the relatively new widespread phenomenon of remote work. This consideration motivates a wider validation approach that will not solely focus on the quantitative validation of the predicted patterns but also on the qualitative validation of the model in terms of ascertaining its usefulness for practical policy analysis tasks. In epistemological terms, in this approach, we seek to utilize the multitude of views and foci of the expert participants to highlight the important links between factors among a multitude of other rather less important links. In other words, we are employing the human intuition of the participants to sieve through the very overwhelmingly large pool of potential factors and their links to find the most important factors and their links. This innately human capability is arguably the most significant hallmark of natural intelligence that provides an advantage to all possible quantitative approaches in that it can efficiently ignore noise and trivia to focus on what matters from a decision-making standpoint concerned with the sustainability of our new ways of life and the potential long-term implications of remote working if spread much more dispersedly and deeply into the fabric of our human society at large.

From a much simpler perspective, it would not be practical or meaningful to seek to model too many factors and their relations quantitatively, not because of limitations in computational power but due to much more basic hurdles in data curation, geospatial harmonization, and collation of meaningful indices or proxy datasets to quantify the factors of interest for the partners. Besides, even if it were possible to make much larger models, the hypothetical Large-Scale Model would arguably be much less useful in terms of explaining how

things work. This is a commonly known issue about Large Scale Models that they tend to be less useful in terms of their explanatory or educational usage when they get bigger and more detailed.

Nevertheless, in the next steps along the development of the R-Map model we seek to quantify the conditional probabilities as the strength values of the causal links in the Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) model that can be characterized as the backbone or the minimum viable product (MVP) version of the R-Map model. In this sense, the only claim to be validated is that this DAG model architecture is rigorously derived from the results of the workshops, and not about it being a complete representation of all there is to remote working arrangements and their ultimate impact on our environs.

6. Conclusions

The most concrete conclusion to be drawn from this task is the consolidated R-Map model presented in Figure 16; this model shows the set of most important factors and their systemic or structural links or causal relationships leading to major impact factors relevant to the general public at global scales. This model architecture can be said to have emerged organically or to have been collectively discovered through a series of disciplined conversations deeply rooted in local and experiential knowledge of the participants from diverse geographical contexts and their idiosyncrasies. Hence, the structure of the model can be taken as a reliable agenda for quantitative research in the next steps of the process.

As extensively explained in the discussion on the limitations of the R-Map model, at this stage of development, one cannot make clear-cut conclusions about [how exactly] what leads to what in terms of the impacts of RWA. In that sense, the conclusions are rather methodological and intermediary rather than being final, factual, and revealing in terms of causal explanations or predictions. The most important conclusion so far is that the combination of PSM and BBN approaches to causal and probabilistic graphical modelling are suited to the complicated/wicked problem of policy analysis and integrated (i.e. multi-sectoral) impact assessment at hand. Despite the challenges ahead of the next steps of the modelling endeavour in terms of data collection, data collation, spatial and temporal harmonization, and alike, one can see that the frequentist statistical alternative approaches to this problem would only make it more confusing, more reductive, less participatory, and arguably less explanatory and thus less useful as to the purpose of the model as a policy analysis and deliberation tool. We argue that we have gained methodological confidence that the R-Map model is gradually taking a useful shape while we are systematically sifting through a multitude of things to be included in the model in favour of highlighting and eliciting the essential variables that can help us get a grip of the transitional impacts brought about by the RWA. There is yet much quantitative work to be done on the model but so far, the conceptual model architecture has stabilized into a shape that can be arguably labelled as collectively validated and systematically consolidated. It must be noted that the very scoping and identification of the inner systemic links in such a large-scale impact assessment model is far from trivial, especially when regarded from a usability and utilitarian perspective of prospective stakeholders.

7. References

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8. Annex

8.1 Annex 1

The table below lists the names of participants in the co-design workshop.

#	First Name	Last Name	Partner Institute
1	Margarita	Angelidou	Q-PLAN
2	Henk	Bouwman	METREX
3	Mariana	Faver	Architecture Urbanism Bureau Thuis (AUBT) (AB member)
4	Katharina	Fellnhofer	RIM
5	Johannes	Flacke	UT
6	Lisa	Fontanella	UB
7	Mandy	Franz	RWW (WFA)
8	Barbara	Glinser	Centre for Social Innovation (AB member)
9	Theodora	Istoriou	AUTH
10	Ozge	Karanfil	KU
11	İlker	Kayı	KU
12	Eirini	Kelmali	SEERC
13	Sibel	Kiran	KU
14	Anna	Konstantinidou	WR
15	Vidit	Kundu	UT
16	Richa	Maheshwari	University of Liège
17	Konstantina	Mataftsi	WR
18	Thomas	Mone	AUTH
19	Pirouz	Nourian	UT

20	Hakan	Orer	KU
21	Karen	Oude Hengel	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO), (AB member)
22	Panagiotis	Papanikolaou	Arx.Net
23	Karin	Pfeffer	UT
24	Dimitra	Plastara	AUTH
25	Georgia	Pozoukidou	AUTH
26	Elli	Roma-Athanasiadou	Q-PLAN
27	Efstratios	Stylianidis	AUTH
28	Vinod	Subramaniam	Twente Board
29	Jasmijn	Tiemersma	CBS
30	Dimitris	Tselios	NOMAD365 (AB member)
31	Cihan	Urhan	Turkish Confederation of Employer Associations (TISK) (AB member)
32	Jon	Wang	UT
33	Anders	Wilandson	Stockholm Region (AB member)
34	Shi (Tracy)	Xu	SURREY
35	Savas	Zafer Sahin	Citizens' Assembly of Ankara (AB member)
36	Nikos	Zaharis	SEERC

Annex Table 1: Co-design workshop participants.

8.2 Annex 2

The table below shows the different factors as agreed during table discussions in the co-design workshop.

Table	Factors
1.1	Decentralisation and new centralities, diversification/ land-use change, urban sprawl/densification and land take, access to local amenities and opportunities, demand for larger housing, digital infrastructure accessibility, caring, access to support network, total number of burnouts, housing affordability, co-living and community building
2.1	Shift in modes of transport, acceptability, cost of living, multilocality, communication and information quality, work life balance capacity, accessibility to public services, individual characteristics, urban/rural divide, gender distribution, household dynamics related burdens
3.1	Internet quality (affordability) and performance, flexibility (location), flexibility (work time), loneliness, insurance, level of inequalities, city size
4.1	Level of digital capacity, digital infrastructure, gentrification, care responsibilities, land consumption, energy demand, attachment and commitment, gender equality, city facilities (transport, health care, amenities), health & safety outside office, employee productivity, precarious job conditions, labour market, mental health
5.1	RWA literacy, autonomy (individual), labour participation, connectivity, precarity, inequality

Table 2: Key factors arrived at after table discussions in the UT co-design workshop

8.3 Annex 3

The table with impact factor definitions is provided below.

#	Factor	Type	Definition	Rationale
1.	Health and Wellbeing	Social Impact	Task 1.3 defines health and wellbeing as outcomes (impacts) including physical health, mental health, social and family, work-related needs, and health behaviours - physical activity, diet, and sleep (according to EU-OSHA, 2023a). Also, the WHO emphasizes a holistic approach to well-being, encompassing physical, mental, and social dimensions to promote overall health and quality of life (WHO, 1948; Topp et. al., 2015)	As described, remote working arrangements encompass specific working conditions and organizational structures that generate psychosocial factors. These factors could potentially serve as sources or conditions that expose individuals to various biopsychosocial influences. Psychosocial factors, in turn, are closely linked to biological outcomes, potentially impacting health, illness, and the development of diseases.
2.	Polycentricity	Spatial Impact	The spatial phenomenon where at a regional scale multiple cities of similar size and importance exist; and at an urban scale multiple neighbourhoods or centres of similar importance exist	As described by T1.2, polycentricity could be a multi-scale phenomenon. At a regional scale, it implies the rise of small/medium sized cities due to RWAs, while at a metropolitan scale it implies decentralisation towards the outskirts of the city
3.	Land Consumption	Spatial Impact	Land consumption can be defined as the expansion of built-up area for human settlements. Task 1.2 defines land consumption in terms of expansion of residential areas into previously undeveloped areas (due to more affordable housing options, less congestion and proximity to nature)	
4.	Work-life Balance	Socio-economic Impact	Time management and boundary settings between work and personal life, and the impact on family and social life; the ability of balance professional responsibilities with personal life (report T1.3 p. 56)	Work-life balance involves not only time management but also workload-related flexibility when needed. There are two key interfaces: a work-related supportive side and a life-related supportive side, each including various supportive services

5.	Caring Responsibilities	Social Impact	Defined in D1.3 as caring responsibilities, that includes housework, childcare, care for elderly, relatives.	
6.	Employee Productivity	Economic Impact	Employee productivity refers to how efficiently and effectively a worker or a group of workers contribute to accomplishing organizational goals	
7.	Multilocality	Spatial Impact	T1.2 defines multilocality as the maintaining of residences and activities in multiple geographic locations.	Greinke and Lange (2022), in their study in three rural districts in Germany, report that multilocality prevents complete relocation from rural to urban areas due to strong ties to family and friends. The potential impacts discussed include housing prices being driving up, new construction, reduced affordability and vacancy in rural areas (Greinke and Lange, 2022; Weichhart and Rumpolt, 2015); increased land consumption, travel distance and car-based commute, benefits to local economy, but pose a challenge in developing strong social ties and engagement in local civic activities (Danielzyk et al., 2020a; Dittrich Wesbuer et al., 2015).
8.	Workplace Loneliness	Socio-economic Impact	Defined in report T1.3 as workplace loneliness (in RWA (p. 174), characterized by lack of information quality, supportive leadership, supportive conditions for job demands, and individual psychological states.	As new ways of working evolve, the definition of the "workplace" is also changing. Employee services related to these "new workplace" aspects play a critical role in supporting job engagement, task completion, and providing network support when needed.
9.	Cost of Living	Socio-economic Impact	The amount of money that a person needs to pay for basic needs such as food, shelter, energy	

10.	Mobility Pattern	Spatial Impact	Patterns of human movement facilitated by public or private transportation. This factor mainly encompasses two aspects: the choice of transport modes and the purpose of trips	A shift has been observed in modal split, purpose of trips due an increase in remote work
11.	Access to Labour Market	Economic Impact	Defined as access to a diverse and competitive labour force for an employer. It also has a relevance for employees, who now have a wider access to job opportunities	
12.	Social Cohesion	Social Impact	Defined as the presence or absence of a social ties or social support network. It can be both digital and physical social ties	The factor has potential implications on individual well-being, mental health, loneliness and productivity.
13.	Local or Regional Economic Development	Economic Impact	Economic development of a region through which a region is capable to improve its economic, political, and social welfare.	Areas with higher remote job shares show greater employment resilience, supporting local economies through stable spending and economic growth, particularly in smaller cities, as reported by T1.4
14.	Tourist/ Digital Nomad Living Space Demand	Socio-economic Impact	The demand for living space from increased number of tourists and digital nomads because of remote work	
15	Carbon emissions	Spatial (Env.) Impact	The amount of CA emitted into the atmosphere resulting from transport activities	

Annex Table 3: Definition of impact factors

The table with driver factor definitions is provided below.

#	Factor	Type	Definition	Rationale
1.	Digital Infrastructure Accessibility	Driver	The factor can be defined as access to high quality (in terms of speed and coverage) and affordable internet	Eurofound (2022a) identifies technical infrastructure (e.g., broadband accessibility) as a possible factor which might explain variations in the prevalence of telework noted across different countries, and between urban and rural areas
2.	Access to Local Amenities	Driver	Access to green areas, shopping, recreation, education, sports and community facilities, co-working spaces, etc. Access to local amenities can have a direct implication on the quality of life.	
3.	Transport Accessibility	Driver	Transport accessibility refers to a measure of the ease of reaching (and interacting with) destinations or activities distributed in space. A place with "high accessibility" is one from which many destinations can be reached with relative ease.	
4.	Taxation, Social Security, Insurance Regulations	Driver	Rules and laws governing how individuals and businesses are taxed, including income, sales, and corporate taxes. The factor encompasses tax rate differences between countries, double tax arrangements, social security and insurance frameworks	

Annex Table 4: Definition of driver factors

8.4 Annex 4

The causal maps generated on each of the tables in the co-design workshop.

Annex Figure 1: Causal Map generated on Table 1.2

Annex Figure 2: Causal Map generated on Table 2.2

Annex Figure 3: Causal Map generated on Table 3.2

Annex Figure 4: Causal Map generated on Table 4.2

Annex Figure 5: Causal Map generated on Table 5.2

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